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Title

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency near-patient tests for tafenoquine or primaquine use in Malaria treatment and prophylaxis

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Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency near-patient tests for tafenoquine or primaquine use in Malaria treatment and prophylaxis

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Background

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) enzyme deficiency is one of the most common genetic disorders, affecting an estimated 500 million people worldwide (Luzzatto et al., 2020). G6PD is an integral component of the pentose phosphate pathway in red blood cells which generates NADPH, which then replenishes cellular stores of glutathione. Glutathione is an antioxidant which forms the primary defense mechanism against oxidative stress. In patients with G6PD deficiency, red blood cells are unable to maintain glutathione homeostasis when exposed to oxidative stress resulting in altered membrane integrity and haemolysis (Cappellini and Fiorelli, 2008). Known triggers for haemolysis in G6PD deficiency include medication, certain food items (for example fresh fava beans), or infection. Spontaneous hemolysis in the absence of a trigger is also known to occur in some cases.

A wide variation is noted in the prevalence of G6PD deficiency based on the sampled population but is relatively common in malaria endemic countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia (Nkhoma et al., 2009). In these territories it has an average prevalence of 8%, but ranges up to 15% in most countries, with peaks of up to 30% in certain areas (Nkhoma et al., 2009).

Important clinical implications exist in the testing and diagnosis of G6PD deficiency which inform therapeutic decision making in malaria. People with G6PD deficiency are at risk of acute haemolytic anemia when exposed to two important drugs used in malaria treatment and prophylaxis, primaquine and tafenoquine. Hence, screening for G6PD deficiency is recommended before these drugs are administered. The recommended reference standard for diagnosis of G6PD deficiency relies on spectrophotometric quantification of G6PD enzyme activity, but several near – patient quantitative and qualitative tests are used in healthcare settings.

Target condition being diagnosed G6PD deficiency

G6PD is an enzyme that is essential in responding to oxidative stress (Beutler, 2008; Cappellini and Fiorelli, 2008). The gene for this enzyme is encoded on the X chromosome. Approximately 230 G6PD gene variants with known mutations associated with decreased enzymatic activity (G6PD deficiency) have been described (Luzzatto et al., 2020). Hemolysis is triggered in individuals with G6PD deficiency when they are exposed to circumstances that increase cellular oxidative stress. These circumstances include infections, certain food items such as fresh fava beans, and the antimalarial drugs primaquine and tafenoquine, as well as other medications such as Dapsone and Rasburicase (La Vieille et al., 2019; Luzzatto et al., 2016).

G6PD testing has become an integral part of clinical decision-making on the use of primaquine and tafenoquine in the treatment and prophylaxis of malaria. The World Health Organization (WHO) also recommends screening neonates for G6PD deficiency in all settings where G6PD deficiency is observed in 3% to 5% or more of the male population (1989). A diagnosis of G6PD deficiency is conventionally made when a patient's G6PD enzyme activity is less than 30% that of the activity observed in normal males (Roper et al., 2020). The G6PD gene is on the X chromosome, giving a direct correspondence of genotype to phenotype in males and a clear bi-modal distribution of phenotypes. However, in females one X-chromosome is randomly inactivated during embryonic development producing a continuous distribution of phenotypes from deficient to normal. For this reason, phenotypes in females are usually classified as deficient, intermediate or normal (Domingo et al., 2019). For the purposes of this review, we define intermediate G6PD activity as 30% to 70%

that of the reference standard. The rationale for clinical trials to use this threshold was based on studies on the haemolytic potential of tafenoquine in female volunteers heterozygous for G6PD deficiency (Rueangweerayut et al., 2017) and is primarily based on safety concerns.

Importance of testing for G6PD deficiency in patients with malaria

Malaria is a febrile illness caused by Plasmodium (P) parasites. Five different species of Plasmodium can cause malaria in humans. Of these, *P. vivax* accounts for 20% of cases worldwide (Baird et al., 2003). *Vivax* infections lead to a significant clinical impact especially in children and pregnant women (Howes et al., 2016). Although traditionally described to cause non-severe manifestations it is now well recognized that it has the propensity to present with severe disease (Phyo et al., 2022). There is encouraging data from showing decline in the rates of *P. vivax* between 2000 – 2017. However, these rates have stalled in the past five years for many countries, with particular increases noted in regions affected by political and economic instability (Battle et al., 2019).

Even though *vivax* malaria is characterized by a relatively low number of parasites circulating during the blood stage, compared to other species, it has been shown to relapse within weeks to months following the primary infection. This is mainly due to reactivation of dormant parasitic forms in the liver (hypnozoites). Hypnozoites are also seen in patients with malaria due to *P. ovale*. Relapses increase the overall morbidity and mortality of the disease (Chu and White, 2016). Relapses can represent up to 80% of all *P. vivax* infections and contribute to onward transmission of the disease. Importantly, global burden estimates of malaria do not consider the impact of these latent reservoirs of infection, underestimating the impact of *vivax* malaria (Battle and Baird, 2021).

In order to achieve radical cure (that is, cure and prevention of relapses) in patients with *vivax* and *ovale* malaria, relapses originating from hypnozoites must be prevented. The only drugs that have activity against hypnozoites are the 8-aminoquinolines. This drug class includes primaquine and tafenoquine (Chu et al., 2018). The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved tafenoquine for use in 2018. Tafenoquine and primaquine are also used for prophylaxis against malaria (Chu and Freedman, 2019; Llanos-Cuentas et al., 2019). They also have gametocytocidal activity against the reproductive forms of the parasite, which are necessary for the disease transmission to the vector and the completion of the parasite life cycle. Both tafenoquine and primaquine are known haemolytic drugs in G6PD deficient patients; drug induced haemolysis can lead to life-threatening anemia (Chu and Freedman, 2019; Waters and Edstein, 2012). Due to the risk of this significant adverse event, the WHO recommends testing for G6PD deficiency before using these drugs in patients with malaria (Levine et al., 2015), and the use of low-dose weekly regimen of primaquine for G6PD deficient patients (WHO, 2023).

Index test(s)

Several near-patient diagnostic tests are available for the diagnosis of G6PD deficiency. This includes both qualitative and quantitative assays for G6PD. Qualitative tests determine whether a patient is above or below a given threshold of G6PD activity, whereas a quantitative test can determine the exact level of G6PD enzyme activity. Both types of tests are used in clinical practice. Technical details of these index tests are provided in (Appendix 1). The important diagnostic threshold for G6PD qualitative tests is less than 30% of normal activity (G6PD-deficient). An additional diagnostic threshold for near-patient G6PD quantitative test is 70% of normal activity; a detected activity between 30% and 70% of normal usually identifies an intermediate level of activity in females.

Qualitative tests

Qualitative tests can be used to determine whether an individual is above or below a threshold predetermined by the diagnostic test for G6PD activity. This is usually less than 30% of reference G6PD activity (WHO 2018). Results denoting deficiency indicate that the tested individual has G6PD activity below this threshold and should be considered G6PD-deficient. Normal results mean that the tested individual has G6PD activity above the specified threshold.

G6PD qualitative fluorescent spot test (FST)

The fluorescent spot test (FST) is the most widely used method for qualitative detection of G6PD deficiency (Beutler and Mitchell, 1968). For several decades, FST has been recommended as a qualitative test for G6PD deficiency screening. This test has been used extensively in operational settings to guide patient treatment and to determine which patients should be included in clinical trials. It uses venous or capillary blood to catalyze a reaction that generates a fluorescent product. The level of fluorescence is used for analysis. A moderate or strong fluorescence indicates normal G6PD, whereas a weak or absent fluorescence indicates G6PD deficiency. Although the FST cannot be used as a point-of-care (POC) test, it can economically be customized for in-health facility use in near-patient settings equipped with electricity

Lateral flow tests

Lateral flow tests for G6PD consist of a plastic or paper cartridge containing a pad that holds reagents. These reagents react to G6PD enzyme activity and change colour based on the activity level in the sample. Samples of either capillary or venous whole blood can be used with this type of test. The CareStart G6PD (CSG) (Adu-Gyasi et al., 2015) and BinaxNOWG6PD (Devine et al., 2017) are qualitative lateral flow diagnostic tests. In these two tests, results are presented in binary form, G6PD deficient and normal phenotype. This is based on a user's visual read of colour change. In the BinaxNOW test, persistence of red colour in the sample front indicates G6PD deficiency (less than 30% of reference activity). In the CSG, lack of colour change in the solution indicates G6PD deficiency (less than 30% of reference activity). Unlike the FST, lateral flow tests can be used as POC tests in clinical and field settings under specific conditions (i.e. optimum temperature recommendations for BinaxNow).

WST8/1-methoxy phenazine methosulfate (PMS) method

The principle of the chemical reactions for detection of G6PD activity is that the hydrogen of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) (produced by G6PD) converts water-soluble tetrazolium salt-8 (WST-8) to WST-8 formazan in the presence of a hydrogen carrier, 1-methoxy phenazine methosulfate (PMS). This gives an easily detectable orange colour, with colour intensity directly proportional to G6PD activity. Samples with normal G6PD activity show a strong orange colour and deficient samples show a faint colour (likely to represent intermediate phenotypes) or no colour (G6PD deficiency and negative controls) (De Niz et al., 2013).

Quantitative tests

The general disadvantage of the above-mentioned qualitative tests is that they can only identify patients whose G6PD activity is below 30% of the normal. Tested individual with a non-deficient result have activity ranging from >30% up to 100% of normal. Subjects on the lower end of this normal range, i.e. heterozygous women with intermediate enzymatic activity, are still susceptible to hemolysis when treated with oxidative drugs. Therefore, in women a 'normal' diagnosis by qualitative testing does not correspond to absence of haemolytic risk during treatment with

oxidative drugs (Chu et al., 2017). During clinical trials, G6PD-heterozygous women with intermediate G6PD activity defined as 30% to 70% of the reference standard, who tested normal by a qualitative test, underwent significant hemoglobin drops with standard anti-relapse primaquine and tafenoquine regimens (Chu et al., 2018). Quantitative tests measure G6PD activity in a whole blood sample and provide a quantitative result for G6PD activity. They also normalize the G6PD activity by the haemoglobin concentration and correct for the influence of temperature on enzymatic activity. This allows quantitative tests to detect intermediate G6PD activity in heterozygous female individuals, by applying the appropriate activity thresholds.

The “Standard G6PD test” by SD Biosensor (Pal et al., 2018) and the CareStart G6PD Biosensor (Pal et al., 2018) by AccessBio are tests that provide a quantitative reading of G6PD activity. Both of these tests provide results within minutes and can be used at the POC. The CareStart G6PD Biosensor combines a haemoglobin measurement device with a G6PD activity measurement device. It then calculates the G6PD activity, normalized for haemoglobin concentration, based on the two measurements. The Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor is designed to measure the quantitative concentration of total haemoglobin and G6PD enzymatic activity at the same time on either capillary or venous blood using a colourimetric method. Both tests produce a numeric value indicating the G6PD enzymatic activity expressed in Unit per grams of hemoglobin.

Clinical pathway

G6PD testing is important for the clinician when making therapeutic decisions on treatment and prophylaxis of malaria in relation to the use of primaquine and tafenoquine. Primaquine and tafenoquine are used for radical cure for *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* malaria. This is due to the efficacy of the drug in eradicating the dormant forms within the liver (hypnozoites) and interrupting the life cycle of the parasite. A radical cure prevents relapses and reduces transmission of the disease. The distinct advantage of tafenoquine over primaquine is that it can be used as single-dose therapy, instead of the 7 or 14-day course. In addition, tafenoquine is also licensed for use in malaria prophylaxis (Chu and Freedman, 2019). Both tafenoquine and primaquine have the propensity to trigger life threatening hemolysis in individuals with G6PD deficiency (Chu and Freedman, 2019; Waters and Edstein, 2012), which leads to a necessity for G6PD testing before administration of these drugs (Levine et al., 2015). Clinical decision-making pathways differ for the use of primaquine and tafenoquine and are summarized below and in [figure 1](#).

Decision-making pathway for primaquine in the treatment of malaria

The WHO's current recommendation is to test patients for G6PD deficiency whenever feasible, before administering primaquine in the management of *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* malaria to achieve a radical cure. The decision pathway depends on the availability of G6PD testing in the clinical setting (World Health, 2018).

When testing for G6PD deficiency is available

When G6PD testing is available males with more than 30% G6PD activity as diagnosed with a qualitative test can be treated with the standard 14-day regimen of primaquine or the 7-day regimen of primaquine 0.5mg/kg daily (total dose 3.5mg/kg). However, a qualitative test cannot clearly differentiate intermediate G6PD activity in females and in the absence of a quantitative G6PD test standard regimen primaquine treatment should be given with patient counselling and monitoring for evidence of haemolysis. In patients who are diagnosed as G6PD deficient with less than 30% G6PD activity, primaquine may be given at a dose of 0.75 mg base/kg once a week for 8 weeks under close medical supervision for potential primaquine-induced hemolysis.

In 2022, WHO endorsed a 7-day regimen (0.5 mg/kg per day, total dose 3.5 mg/kg primaquine), which is implemented in India and several countries in South America (WHO, 2021). A higher dose regimen (7 mg/kg total dose) given over 7 days (1.0 mg/kg per day) has been shown to be non-inferior to the same total dose given over 14 days (0.5 mg/kg per day) (Taylor et al., 2019). In the recently published PRIMA study, a high-dose short-course of primaquine in patients with a G6PD activity of 70% or greater, was safe and relatively well tolerated and reduced the risk of subsequent *P. vivax* parasitaemia compared to single dose of 0.25 mg/kg oral primaquine (Thriemer et al., 2023).

When testing for G6PD deficiency is unavailable

In cases where testing is not available, a decision for administration of primaquine for radical cure of *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* is made based on risk-benefit stratification given the potential consequences of malaria relapses. Aspects factored into the decision-making process include the prevalence and severity of G6PD deficiency in the local population, and the capacity of local health systems to recognize and treat primaquine-induced hemolysis, including the availability of blood transfusion. If a decision is made not to administer primaquine, the patient is advised on when to return to seek treatment for a suspected relapse.

Clinical pathway for tafenoquine in the treatment of malaria

Current recommendations for tafenoquine indicate that the drug should only be prescribed to those with G6PD activity that is greater than 70% of the local population median (reference activity). This requires all females being considered for tafenoquine to undergo quantitative testing for G6PD. The rationale for requiring quantitative G6PD testing is that heterozygous females with intermediate G6PD activity are also at risk for tafenoquine-induced hemolysis. This risk is further compounded by the fact that tafenoquine has a longer half-life, compared to primaquine and drug exposure cannot be stopped at the first signs of hemolysis (Rueangweerayut et al., 2017). To date apart from the original publication on tafenoquine by Rueangweerayut et al in female healthy volunteers heterozygous (Rueangweerayut et al., 2017), published studies using tafenoquine have included only G6PD-normal individuals. Some studies specifically included only those participants with a G6PD activity that was greater than 70% of the population median (reference activity), which for safety reasons is therefore proposed as the upper limit of the intermediate threshold (Chu and Freedman, 2019).

Tafenoquine for prophylaxis of malaria

Tafenoquine is licensed for use in the prophylaxis of malaria. This is primarily due to its effects on the transmission of *P. falciparum* gametocytes. Primaquine has a similar effect, but is not in widespread use due to its daily dosing schedule. Due to the risk of hemolysis, all individuals considered for prophylaxis with tafenoquine should undergo G6PD testing prior to administration.

Figure 1 – Clinical pathway for near patient qualitative and quantitative tests for G6PD deficiency

Alternative tests for G6PD deficiency not included in this review

Genetic tests

Genetic tests use DNA analysis methods to detect mutations within the G6PD gene. These tests are predominantly used in large population studies and have poor utility in clinical practice. Genetic tests that focus on single nucleotide polymorphisms may miss detection of patients with G6PD deficiency with mutations not included in the reference panel. Sequencing methods can detect novel mutations that require subsequent phenotypic confirmation. Neither DNA sequencing nor polymerase chain reaction can measure the relative proportion of G6PD-deficient to G6PD-normal red blood cell populations in heterozygous females (World Health, 2018).

Cytochemical assay methods

These methods provide information on intracellular G6PD levels and could be utilized for observation of the relative proportions of deficient to normal cells in heterozygous females. However, most of these methods requires equipped laboratory and complex techniques and are therefore only used in research studies.

Rationale for the review

Effective treatment of *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* malaria is dependent on gametocidal activity and radical cure against hypnozoites. The 8-aminoquinolines, primaquine or tafenoquine, are currently indicated for this purpose. It is notable that the failure to prevent relapse through achieving radical cure incurs risk of serious illness and death with *P. vivax* malaria (Baird, 2015). As discussed above, these medications have a propensity to trigger hemolysis in patients with G6PD deficiency. The current gold standard test for diagnosis of G6PD deficiency is quantitative spectrophotometry. However, this

is an expensive technique that requires optimum laboratory conditions and equipment. Furthermore, the results of the test may not be available in time to guide clinical decisions. Most populations with high prevalence of G6PD deficiency live in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) where this test is available only in specialized hospitals or is not available at all. Qualitative tests provide valuable information in differentiating individuals at a level of 30% G6PD activity, which in most cases is the threshold for treatment with standard dose primaquine. Over the years, several rapid diagnostic qualitative tests have been introduced to clinical practice for diagnosis of G6PD deficiency. A comparative analysis of these qualitative tests would be instrumental in the development of guidelines on test choices in clinical practice. The recent FDA approval of tafenoquine may place more importance on quantitative G6PD assay methods, as administration of the drug requires demonstration of G6PD activity that is greater than 70% of the local population median (reference activity). In this light, it is imperative that a diagnostic accuracy analysis be performed for rapid diagnostic quantitative tests for G6PD deficiency. Based on the justification presented above, the findings of this review will have high impact in informing management decisions in *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* malaria.

Objectives

Primary objective

To assess the diagnostic accuracy of near-patient tests for G6PD deficiency in people undergoing treatment or prophylaxis with primaquine or tafenoquine for malaria, or in people at risk of or susceptible to malaria.

Secondary objectives

- To perform direct and indirect comparisons of diagnostic accuracy based on test brands and test types
- To investigate sources of heterogeneity, namely the following.
 - Age: adults versus children
 - Sex: male versus female
 - Reported prevalence of G6PD (high versus low)
 - Malaria endemicity (endemic versus non-endemic)
 - Geographic location (continent of residence; that is, Africa, Asia, or another continent)
 - Reference standard used (adjusted male median, median G6PD, laboratory standard, manufacturer standard)
 - Type of blood used (venous versus capillary)
 - To compare the accuracy of each brand and type of test.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

Diagnostic accuracy studies are typically cross-sectional in design. This review included cross-sectional studies that compared the index test to the current diagnostic gold standard test, as well as studies that performed comparative analyses between different index tests. Diagnostic test accuracy studies performed at the baseline of randomized trials were also considered cross-sectional and were therefore included. Within the cross-sectional design, a diagnostic test accuracy study could be conducted in a 'single-gate' or 'two-gate' orientation. In the single-gate orientation, a single set of inclusion criteria was used for the inclusion of participants. In the 'two-gate' orientation, different sets of criteria were used for those with and those without the target condition. This review included studies with both single-gate and two-gate orientations, though the latter was prone to overestimation of accuracy (Rutjes et al., 2006). The risk of bias from 'two-gate' studies was recorded using the "Revised Tool for the Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies" (QUADAS-2) (Whiting et al., 2011) and the effect on the overall accuracy estimates was also assessed through a sensitivity analysis.

Participants

This review included participants who were eligible to be considered for treatment or prophylaxis of malaria with primaquine and tafenoquine. Although the final analysis and interpretation of this review were mostly instrumental in management decisions in malaria, the diagnostic accuracy of studies that evaluated the selected index tests were not restricted to patients with malaria or to populations in malaria-endemic areas. This was because valid data on the diagnostic accuracy of the index tests could be extracted irrespective of the population characteristics. The inclusion of data

from testing in healthy volunteers was also relevant for the use of primaquine and tafenoquine as prophylaxis against the disease.

Studies providing data on the diagnostic accuracy of the index tests in neonates were excluded. This was because G6PD activity is higher in the neonatal period compared to other age groups and may also vary by ethnicity. This generates unique reference ranges and reference standards for diagnosis of G6PD deficiency in this population. Furthermore, performance of the index tests in neonates is likely to be different in comparison to studies in older populations (Kaplan et al., 2005; Keihanian et al., 2017)

Index tests

The index tests included in the review are as follows.

Qualitative tests

- G6PD Qualitative FST
- CareStart G6PD
- BinaxNOW G6PD
- WST8/1-methoxy PMS assay

The brilliant cresyl blue (BCB) discoloration test, the methemoglobin reduction test, the formazan ring method, and the ephadex gel MTT-PMS method were excluded from the review, as they were not used in routine clinical practice.

Quantitative tests

- Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor
- CareStart G6PD Biosensor by AccessBio

FST

In the G6PD qualitative fluorescent spot test (FST), phenotypic determination is performed by incubating a few μL of venous or capillary blood with glucose-6-phosphate and NADP in the substrate reagent and spotting the residual on filter paper. The dried spots are then viewed under long-wave ultraviolet (UV) light to detect the fluorescent by product NADPH. Detected fluorescence is directly proportional to G6PD activity and lack of fluorescence signals G6PD deficiency (Beutler and Mitchell, 1968). Depending on the brand of FST, fluorescence is read at both 5 and 10 minutes or directly at 10 minutes. The following fluorescence levels are used for analysis:

- Normal G6PD activity: (moderate to strong fluorescence after 5 minutes) strong fluorescence after 10 minutes.
- Deficient G6PD activity: weak or no fluorescence after (5 and) 10 minutes. Lateral flow tests for G6PD consist of a plastic or paper cartridge containing a pad that holds reagents. These reagents react to G6PD enzyme activity and change colour based on the activity level in the sample.

Samples of either capillary or venous whole blood can be used with this type of test.

CareStart G6PD and BinaxNow

The CareStart G6PD and BinaxNOW G6PD are qualitative lateral flow diagnostic tests. In these two tests results are presented in binary form with deficiency diagnosed on a single activity threshold of $\lesssim 30\%$.

BinaxNow

The BinaxNOW G6PD test device consists of a lateral flow test strip comprised of a white sample pad and a reaction pad. The reaction pad contains the reagents necessary for the G6PD enzymatic reaction and the subsequent reduction of a nitro blue tetrazolium dye into its concomitant blue formazan product. The resulting colour change on the strip indicates enough G6PD activity is present to presume the sample is not deficient. To perform the test, a whole venous blood sample is mixed with RBC lysing reagent in a sample preparation vial and then transferred to the test device sample pad. The lysed blood sample migrates up the test strip, reconstituting reagents in the reaction pad. Test results are read visually. If no change in the red colour of the sample front is observed at the test read time, the sample is presumed to be deficient in G6PD enzyme activity. Samples normal in G6PD activity produce a distinct colour change - the red sample colour changes to a brown/black colour on the upper half of the reaction pad (Osorio 2015).

CareStart G6PD

The CareStart G6PD is a qualitative enzyme chromatographic test based on the reduction of colourless nitro blue tetrazolium dye to dark coloured formazan (Adu-Gyasi 2015). This is a qualitative enzyme chromatographic test based on the reduction of colourless nitro blue tetrazolium dye to dark coloured formazan. Two μL of venous blood are added into the sample well with two drops of buffer into the buffer well. The G6PD deficiency status of an individual is read in 10 minutes. Samples with normal G6PD activity produce a distinct purple colour background in the result window while no colour change is observed for samples with deficient G6PD activity (Kim 2011).

WST-8

The principle of the WST8/1-methoxy PMS method is based on reduction of hydrogen from NADPH which converts WST8 to WST8-formazan in the presence of the hydrogen carrier 1-methoxy-PMS (Niz 2013). This reaction yields a strong easily detectable orange colour, with a colour intensity directly proportional to G6PD activity. Following a 2-hour incubation at room temperature, samples with normal activity demonstrate a strong orange colour. Deficient samples can show a faint orange colour which represents moderate deficiency or no colour which indicates severe deficiency.

Quantitative tests

Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor and the CareStart G6PD Biosensor by AccessBio are tests that provide a quantitative reading of G6PD activity. Additional classification into "Deficient", "Intermediate" and "Normal" phenotypes can be obtained using calculated or pre-set thresholds of activity.

CareStart G6PD Biosensor

The CareStart G6PD Biosensor consolidates a haemoglobin measurement device with a G6PD activity measurement device. The device consolidates a haemoglobin measurement device with a G6PD activity measurement device. This then calculates the G6PD activity normalized for haemoglobin concentration based on the two measurements. Requires 5 μL of whole blood for G6PD and 7 μL for Hb assessment (Bancone 2018). Results are presented in IU/gHb.

Standard G6PD biosensor

The Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor is designed to measure the quantitative concentration of total haemoglobin (g/dL) and G6PD enzymatic activity (IU/g Hb) in fresh human whole blood based on reflectometry assays. This requires 10 µL of capillary or venous blood. Results are presented in IU/gHb (Pal 2019). The Standard G6PD test contains a flow through Standard G6PD test device treated membrane and mesh. The test is based on the colorimetric measuring and quantitative detection system for automatic calculation of the code chip on each test device. G6PD catalyzes the first step in the pentose phosphate pathway (PPP), oxidizing glucose-6-phosphate (G6P) to 6-phosphogluconolactone and reducing nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) to reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH). When NADPH is generated by the Standard G6PD Test, 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl-phosphate (BCIP) and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) are reduced by the diaphorase reaction and then yield a violet colour, which is directly proportional to the concentration of G6PD present in the specimens. The colour intensity can be measured numerically by checking the specific absorbance of the reduced BCIP and NBT, and the test result is displayed on the Standard G6PD Analyzer's screen by processing the pre-programmed algorithm.

Target conditions

The target condition was G6PD deficiency. The sensitivity and specificity of the index tests to detect the presence of two target conditions were determined: G6PD activity less than 30% of that of the reference standard (indicative of G6PD deficiency); and G6PD activity less than 70% of that of the reference standard (which represented the threshold for the diagnosis of intermediate G6PD activity). Additional analysis was also performed for the 30 – 70% diagnostic thresholds for quantitative G6PD tests in females.

Target conditions

G6PD activity lower than 30% of the reference standard was classified as G6PD deficient. This category encompassed all hemizygous G6PD-deficient males and homozygous G6PD-deficient females. This threshold was defined by WHO for guiding treatment decisions related to primaquine.

G6PD activity lower than 70% of the reference standard was established as the threshold for treatment with single dose tafenoquine and high dose primaquine (1mg/kg) daily for 7 days (Figure 1). This threshold was derived from clinical trials and was based on the upper cutoff level for intermediate G6PD activity. The rationale behind adopting this threshold in clinical trials and for treatment was grounded in studies on the hemolytic potential of tafenoquine in female volunteers who were heterozygous for G6PD deficiency (Rueangweerayut et al., 2017). The 70% cutoff of G6PD activity is readily available with the use of quantitative tests but is estimated by some investigators for qualitative tests. Additional analysis was also performed for the 30 – 70% diagnostic thresholds for quantitative G6PD tests in females.

Reference standards

The reference standards were based on the spectrophotometric assay for G6PD, the gold standard quantitative test for the level of G6PD activity. This provided a quantitative value for G6PD enzyme activity. The spectrophotometry reference standard definitions were based on the following considerations.

A stakeholder group (Domingo et al., 2013), recommended that the reference standard value should be based on the median value of G6PD activity for the entire male population in a given study. If

purposive or biased recruitment was used, the median G6PD value of the G6PD-normal males recruited for the study was used as the definition of normal. If this was not available, an adjusted male median (AMM) could be used as the reference standard. The AMM was calculated by excluding all males with G6PD activity equal to or less than 10% of the male median and determining a new median G6PD activity. This was used as the 100% G6PD activity value from which cut-off levels were defined. For example, a 30% value of the AMM was classified as G6PD-deficient. It was also appreciated that in studies prior to Domingo 2013, the reference standard used might have been a test manufacturer-specified value or a laboratory value determined from male subjects with known normal G6PD status. For studies where the AMM was not reported, it was calculated if the relevant individual data were available for the study. Then, the thresholds for these studies were defined based on the AMM.

This approach was used in a recent meta-analysis by Ley et al. (Ley et al., 2019) Due to the variation in reference standards, a heterogeneity analysis was performed based on the utilized reference standard.

For the Standard G6PD biosensor a supplementary analysis was performed using manufacturer references to calculate relevant thresholds.

Search methods for identification of studies

The search strategy was prepared with the assistance of the CIDG Information Specialist. All relevant studies were attempted to be identified regardless of language, publication status, or publication date limit. The search extended from 1946 to 31st October 2023

Electronic searches

The following databases were searched using the search terms and strategy described in Appendix 1: the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL, published in the Cochrane Library), MEDLINE (via OVID), Embase (accessed via Ovid), and Science Citation Index (Web of Science). Additionally, the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) and ClinicalTrials.gov were searched to identify trials in progress.

Searching other resources

The reference lists of relevant studies were also checked. Articles citing our included studies were searched in the Science Citation Index-Expanded (Web of Science). The "Related articles" feature in PubMed was used to identify additional references.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two review authors (SP and JT) independently determined study eligibility for inclusion by examining the title and abstract of each article identified by the literature search (details of search strategy provided in appendix 1) . A third review author (PW) resolved conflicts when necessary. Two review authors (SP and JT) subsequently obtained the full-text articles for the selected abstracts and assessed them against the prespecified inclusion and exclusion criteria, as defined in the protocol. The two review authors and a third review author (PW) resolved conflicts through discussion. When the review authors could not reach consensus, a fourth review author (EO) made the final decision.

Data extraction and management

Two review authors (SP and JT) performed data extraction and management, with the assistance of PW and GB. A standardized data extraction form was developed, which included the following themes.

- Details of the study: first author, publication year, journal, study design, inclusion/exclusion criteria
- Characteristics of the study population: age, gender (percentage of males and females in the study population), malaria-endemicity of the setting, prevalence of G6PD
- Reference standard: Spectrophotometric assay conditions and interpretation standards
- Index test used: quantitative, qualitative, mixed; type of assay method used; cutoff used for determination of G6PD activity
- Details of the outcome: number of indeterminate, missing, or unavailable test results; number of true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN) results
- Inconsistencies and conflicts in data extraction were resolved by discussion within the review team.

We directly contacted authors for relevant data to obtain missing data and analyses

Assessment of methodological quality

Two review authors independently assessed the quality of each individual study using a modified QUADAS-2 tool (Whiting et al., 2011). Two review authors (SP and JT) independently assessed all included studies using a pre-designed and pre-tested form. This was performed under the supervision of PW and EO. Disagreements were resolved based on discussion and consensus between the two authors and in consultation with the entire review team when consensus between the two designated authors could not be reached.

Statistical analysis and data synthesis

Two-by-two data (the number of TP, TN, FP, and FN results) for each study were entered into Review Manager 5 (RevMan 2020). Estimates of sensitivity and specificity from each individual study were summarized on forest plots, and these estimates were plotted with summary receiver operating characteristics (SROC) plots. When appropriate, given the number of studies, results from the included studies were meta-analyzed. Data from quantitative and qualitative tests were summarized separately. For each type of test (qualitative or quantitative), a common threshold was selected, and the bivariate model was used to obtain pooled estimates of sensitivity and specificity at the common threshold (McCaskill 2010). For instance, selected thresholds were less than 30% for qualitative tests and less than 30% and less than 70% for quantitative tests. The bivariate model was fitted using the 'xtmelogit' commands in Stata version 14 (Stata 2017). Summary estimates of sensitivity and specificity were plotted using SROC plots in Review Manager 5. When the studies allowed, a comparison was made between the accuracy of qualitative tests and quantitative tests. An indirect comparison analysis of diagnostic tests was initially performed in all included studies, followed by a direct comparison in studies that used the test in the same individuals. The accuracy of qualitative and quantitative tests was compared by adding a covariate for test type to the bivariate model. Model fit was assessed by conducting likelihood ratio tests, and the likelihood of the correlation coefficient was profiled to determine if this parameter had been poorly estimated.

Investigations of heterogeneity

The forest plots and SROC plots were first visually examined for heterogeneity. The potential determinants or sources of heterogeneity were analyzed as covariates in the bivariate model. Where possible and appropriate, the following categorical covariates were assessed for heterogeneity:

- Age: adults versus children
- Sex: male versus female
- Reported prevalence of G6PD (high versus low)
- Malaria-endemic versus non-endemic: endemic areas were extracted from maps generated using model-based geo-statistics methods (Gosoni 2006)
- Geographic location (based on continent of residence, for example, Africa, Asia)
- Reference standard used (AMM/median G6PD/laboratory standard)
- Type of blood used (venous versus capillary)

Sensitivity analyses

When there were sufficient data, sensitivity analyses were performed to examine the influence of risk of bias. The impact of risk of bias in each of the four QUADAS-2 domains (patient selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing) was examined by excluding studies at high risk of bias from the main analyses. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis for the included 'two gate' studies was conducted to assess their influence on the risk of bias. The effect of these studies on the overall accuracy estimates was also assessed.

Assessment of reporting bias

We made no formal assessment of reporting bias.

Results

Screening and study selection

A total of 1566 studies fulfilled the above-mentioned criteria for inclusion with a cutoff search date of September 2023. Following exclusion of 10 duplicates a total of 1556 studies were deemed suitable for title and abstract screening. Following abstract and title screening we evaluated 110 studies for full text screening. A total of 82 studies were excluded following full text review. The most common reasons for exclusion were studies evaluating an index test not included within the scope of the review (25.6%) and the use of an inappropriate reference standard (19.5%). This data is summarized in [figure 2](#).

Figure 2 – PRISMA flowchart for selection of studies for the review

Description of included studies

We included 30 studies with a total number of 20861 participants (Adissu et al., 2023) (Abdul-Ghani et al., 2016; Adu-Gyasi et al., 2015; Alam et al., 2018; Bancone et al., 2015; Bancone et al., 2018a; Bancone et al., 2018b; Brito et al., 2016; Dechyotin et al., 2021; Espino et al., 2016; Hamid et al., 2018; Henriques et al., 2018; Kießling et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2011; Kuwahata et al., 2010; LaRue et al., 2014; Ley et al., 2017; Oo et al., 2016; Osorio et al., 2015b; Pal et al., 2019; Pal et al., 2021; Roca-Feltrer et al., 2014; Roh et al., 2016; Satyagraha et al., 2016; von Fricken et al., 2014; Weppelmann et al., 2017; Wojnarski et al., 2020; Zobrist et al., 2021). (Supplementary table 1) Concerning geographic localities of recruitment sites, a total of 13 studies were conducted in Africa and 13 were conducted in Asia. Participants in malarial endemic territories were sampled in the majority of studies (29/30).

Participant characteristics

Of the 30 studies, majority were on adult populations with 3 studies performed on children and 3 studies on a mixed population of adults and children. Most studies included both females and males in their study sample.

Study designs

Index test

For the description of index tests and reference standards report results by study arms as some studies evaluated several tests within their design. Of the study arms included in the review 19/30 study arms evaluated qualitative G6PD index tests and 11/30 evaluated quantitative tests. A total of 8/30 studies evaluated the FST while 14/30 studies evaluated the Carestart G6PD qualitative test. Of the quantitative near patient tests the most commonly studied was the Standard G6PD Biosensor (6/30 of total studies and 6/11 studies that evaluated quantitative tests). Most near patient tests were performed on venous blood. Some studies evaluated the same test in both venous and capillary blood (Adissu 2023 Ethiopia, Adissu 2023 India, Zobrist 2021, Pal 2021, Alam 2018).

Reference Standards

In all studies the reference standard was a spectrophotometric assay. The reference cutoff for G6PD diagnosis was calculated based on the adjusted male median in the majority of studies. Five studies reported G6PD activity in reference to median of males without G6PD. 6 studies reported sensitivity and specificity based on manufacturer recommended cutoff values. We obtained raw data for these studies from the authors and recalculated thresholds based on the AMM for these studies.

Methodological quality of the included studies – analysis of risk of bias (Figure 3, Figure 4)

Data related to Adissu 2023 Ethiopia and India were not published as standalone papers risk of bias analysis was performed using manufacturer supplied protocols and documentation. All other studies were assessed based on information presented in the published paper or protocol wherever available. Detailed analysis of risk of bias is presented in supplementary table 1.

Participant selection

We judged that the majority of studies had low risk of bias with regard to patient selection (15/30; 50.0%) of the remaining 15 studies, 7 were determined high risk due to non – random participant selection and 8 unclear risk due to inadequate reporting on sampling criteria.

Index tests

In this domain of the QUADAS2 We judged 14/30 (46.6%) studies to have conducted or implemented the index test with low risk of bias. The remainder were adjudged as unclear risk of bias exclusively due to insufficient information on whether the index test was conducted without knowledge of the reference standard.

Reference standards

Out of 30 studies 16 were judged unclear risk (46.6%) of bias with regard to the conduct of the reference standard due to insufficient reporting on whether the reference tests were conducted with appropriate blinding from the index tests.

Study	Risk of bias domains			
	D1	D2	D3	D4
Abdul Ghani 2016	+	+	+	-
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia	+	-	-	+
Adissu 2023 India	+	-	-	+
Adu Gyasi 2015	X	+	+	+
Alam 2018	X	-	-	X
Albsheer 2021	X	+	+	+
Aung 2023	-	-	-	+
Bancone 2015	X	-	-	+
Bancone 2018	X	-	-	+
Brito 2016	+	+	+	+
Espino 2016	+	-	-	-
Hamid 2018	+	-	-	-
Henriques 2018	-	+	+	X
Kiesling 2018	X	-	-	+
Kim 2011	-	+	+	+
Kuwahata 2010	-	+	+	-
La Rue 2014	-	-	-	+
Ley 2017	+	-	-	-
Oo 2016	+	+	+	+
Osorio 2015	+	+	+	+
Pal 2018	X	+	+	-
Pal 2021	+	+	+	-
Roca Feltre 2014	+	+	+	+
Roh 2016	+	-	-	+
Satyagraha 2016	+	-	-	-
Sumalai 2021	-	-	-	-
Von Friken 2014	-	-	-	-
Wepelmann 2017	-	-	-	+
Wojnarski 2020	+	+	+	+
Zobrist 2021	+	+	+	+

Domains:
D1: Patient selection.
D2: Index test.
D3: Reference standard.
D4: Flow & timing.

Judgement
 High
 Some concerns
 Low

Figure 3 – Risk of Bias of included studies

Flow and timing

There is uncertainty of the optimum timing between the index and reference tests as well as effects of sample storage on G6PD tests making it challenging to make determination on this domain. For this rating we used an interval separation of 24 hours or less as low risk of bias . We determined unclear flow related risk of bias in 10/30 (33.3%) studies due to insufficient reporting on timing between reference and index tests. 2 studies were determined as high risk of bias as not all participants were not included in the analysis.

Figure 4 – Summary plot for risk of bias

Test details and related contextual factors in relation to applicability of the evaluated near patient G6PD tests

From the studies evaluated it was possible to extract data on the study setting and circumstances of the index and reference test. We have summarized this data below along with a description of the index tests. Full details on applicability analysis is provided in [Supplementary table 1](#). In all instances the reference test was performed in the laboratory.

FST

In all studies that evaluated the FST in the systematic review (Satyagraha 2016, Bancone 2015, Espino 2016, Henriques 2018, Oo 2016, La Rue 2014, Roca – Feltrer 2014 and Sumalai 2021) the index test was performed in laboratory settings. This is reflective of the fact that the applicability of the study is limited at a point of care and requires laboratory facilities and UV light to read and interpret results. All FSTs were performed by trained laboratory technicians.

BinaxNow

Of the studies considered in the systematic review (Kuwahata 2010 and La Rue 2014) the test was conducted in the field. Kuwahata 2010 performed the BinaxNow test in the field within 20 minutes of blood collection. In La Rue 2014 this test was performed on the same day as blood collection. Of note is that there is a manufacturer recommended optimal temperature for conduct of this test (18°C and 25°C)(Osorio et al., 2015a).

CareStart G6PD

Of the studies that evaluated the CareStart G6PD there was a variation in where the index test was conducted. In a majority of studies (Abdul Ghani 2016, Adu Gyasi 2015, Alam 2018, Albsheer 2021, Brito 2016, Kim 2011, Ley 2017, Roca Feltrer 2014, Roh 2016, Satyagraha 2016, Wojnarski 2017) the test was performed in the field by study personnel. Of note, Wojnarski reports that healthcare workers and Village Malaria workers were trained to conduct the test for purpose of the study. However, in some studies (Bancone 2015, Bancone 2018, Espino 2016, Henriques 2018, Von Friken 2014) collected samples were transported to the laboratory following collection. The time range for which these samples were stored for range for 6 – 48 hours. Of note these studies do not report user perspectives or difficulty of interpretation in the use of these tests and this analysis is beyond the scope of the review.

WST-8

Of the studies that evaluated the WST – 8, two studies (Ley 2017, Kuwahata 2010) were performed in field settings. Espino 2016 performed the test on collected blood samples following storage. In this study all samples were stored at 4–8°C and 73% of the venous blood samples were analysed within two days after collection.

Quantitative tests

CareStart G6PD Biosensor

For studies evaluating the CareStart G6PD biosensor, two studies (Hamid 2018 and Ley 2017) performed the test in the field immediately following sample collection. Three studies (Aung 2023, Alam 2018, Wepelmann 2017) performed the test on blood samples stored at 4C.

Standard G6PD biosensor

In studies evaluating the Standard G6PD biosensor Alam 2018 performed the test immediately after collection of blood in the field. In the study Pal 2018, samples in the US arm were stored at 4°C until processing 2- 4 days later and those in the Thailand arm were stored at 4°C until analysis (time not stated). In the study of Pal 2021 samples from the UK and US were on venous blood and capillary blood. Capillary blood testing was done in the field and venous blood analysis was performed in laboratory settings. Venous blood processing in this study was performed within 72 hours of collection on specimens stored at 4-6°C. A similar testing model in the field and laboratory was undertaken in Zobrist 2021 where the study was conducted in Manaus Brazil. In Adissu 2023 (Ethiopia) capillary samples were tested in the field. For venous samples, specimens were stored at 4-6°C immediately after collection and transferred to the laboratory. Reference testing by spectrophotometry was conducted within 72-hours of collection. A similar protocol of sample processing was undertaken for Adissu 2023 India. For all Standard G6PD studies performed in the field the test was performed by trained healthcare workers.

Of note, the data from Pal 2021 contains a set of 90 contrived samples intended to increase the number of specimens in the intermediate G6PD activity range. Here specimens were collected, shipped and stored at 4-6°C until testing. Specimens were split into two aliquots: one aliquot was refrigerated, and the other aliquot was incubated in a temperature-controlled water bath. Both aliquots were used to create the contrived panel. All testing was completed within 24-hours of sample panel generation.

Findings

Qualitative near patient G6PD tests

Pooled analysis of qualitative tests at the 30% threshold by test brands

Of the studies that evaluated qualitative test diagnostic accuracy (Figure 5), most focused on the Carestart G6PD and G6PD qualitative FST. A total of 15 study arms with a total of 9552 participant samples evaluated the Carestart G6PD test at a 30% threshold, with pooled sensitivity of 94.8% (89.3% - 97.6%) and pooled specificity of 96.4% (93.4 – 98.1%). For the G6PD qualitative FST at a 30% threshold a total of 8 studies and 5150 patient samples were evaluated. The pooled sensitivity (98.1%; 96.3 – 99.0) and pooled specificity (95.4%; 91.6 – 97.6%) were comparable to the Carestart G6PD at this threshold. A pooled analysis could not be performed due to inadequate studies for the BinaxNow and WST – 8 /1 – methoxy PMS assay. (Table 1)

Pooled analysis for all qualitative tests at a 30% threshold

We then performed a combined analysis for all qualitative tests considering the 30% threshold. This analysis included 19 study arms at 11456 patient samples. The pooled sensitivity was 94.9% (89.4 – 97.6%) and specificity was 96.2% (93.5% - 97.8%) (Table 2)

Pooled analysis for all qualitative tests at the 70% threshold by test brands

For the Carestart G6PD test when considering the 70% threshold which was reported in 5 study arms and 2653 patient samples and we noted a lower sensitivity of 52.5 (35.4 - 69.1%) and similar specificity to the 30% threshold (97.1%). When considering pooled analysis for the G6PD qualitative FST, similar comparative trends were noted at 30% and 70% thresholds (Table 1).

Pooled analysis for all qualitative tests at a 70% threshold

Pooled analysis for all qualitative tests at the 70% threshold included 6 study arms with 3298 patient samples. The pooled sensitivity for this analysis was 70.9% (44.3 – 88.1%) and specificity was 94.8% (90.3 – 97.3%) (Table 2)

CareStart G6PD 30%

CareStart G6PD 70%

G6PD Qualitative FST 30%

G6PD Qualitative FST 70%

BinaxNOW G6PD 30%

WST8/1-methoxy PMS 30%

WST8/1-methoxy PMS 70%

Figure 5 – Forest plots of qualitative G6PD tests

Direct and Indirect comparisons between qualitative near patient G6PD tests

Direct comparisons between test brands for qualitative near patient G6PD tests

Kuwahata 2010 directly compared the accuracy of WST8/1-methoxy PMS and BinaxNOW G6PD at the 30% threshold value (Figure 6). There was no evidence to suggest a difference in the sensitivity between the two brands (Table 3) with an absolute difference (95% Confidence Interval (CI)) of 16.7 (-13.2 to 46.5). The difference in specificity was 0.0, with both tests having a specificity of 100.0%. However, the results should be interpreted with caution due to the small number of participants recruited in this study (n=20).

CareStart G6PD 30%

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Bancone 2015 (b)	42	2	5	101	0.89 [0.77, 0.96]	0.98 [0.93, 1.00]
Satyagraha 2016	29	28	1	552	0.97 [0.83, 1.00]	0.95 [0.93, 0.97]
Oo 2016	66	79	2	853	0.97 [0.90, 1.00]	0.92 [0.90, 0.93]
Bancone 2015 (a)	47	14	0	89	1.00 [0.92, 1.00]	0.86 [0.78, 0.92]
Roca Feltrer 2014	74	26	0	838	1.00 [0.95, 1.00]	0.97 [0.96, 0.98]

G6PD Qualitative FST 30%

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Satyagraha 2016	28	45	2	535	0.93 [0.78, 0.99]	0.92 [0.90, 0.94]
Bancone 2015 (b)	45	2	2	101	0.96 [0.85, 0.99]	0.98 [0.93, 1.00]
Bancone 2015 (a)	46	1	1	102	0.98 [0.89, 1.00]	0.99 [0.95, 1.00]
Oo 2016	67	26	1	906	0.99 [0.92, 1.00]	0.97 [0.96, 0.98]
Roca Feltrer 2014	74	21	0	843	1.00 [0.95, 1.00]	0.98 [0.96, 0.98]

Figure 6 – Direct comparisons between Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST at the 30% threshold

Espino 2016 compared WST8/1-methoxy PMS and G6PD Qualitative FST in the same population at the 30% and 70% threshold values. At the 30% threshold, there was evidence to suggest a difference in the sensitivity and specificity between the two test brands (Table 4). The sensitivity of WST8/1-methoxy PMS was 84.2%, significantly lower than the 96.5% for G6PD Qualitative FST with an absolute difference (95% CI) of 12.3 (1.7 to 22.9, p=0.026). Whereas the specificity of G6PD Qualitative FST was 95.2%, significantly lower than the 98.2% for WST8/1-methoxy PMS with a difference (95% CI) of 3.0 (0.9 to 5.1, p=0.005). At the 70% threshold, there was evidence to suggest a significant difference in the sensitivity between the two test brands, but not in the specificity. The sensitivity of WST8/1-methoxy PMS was 38.8%, significantly lower than the 55.2% for G6PD Qualitative FST with an absolute difference (95% CI) of 16.4 (4.6 to 28.2, p=0.007). The difference in specificity (95% CI) was 0.4 (-1.1 to 1.9).

Satyagraha 2016 compared Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST in the same population at the 30% and 70% threshold values. At the 30% threshold for Carestart G6PD there was evidence to suggest a significant difference in the specificity between the two tests (Table 5), but not in the sensitivity. The specificity of G6PD Qualitative FST was 90.7%, significantly lower than the 95.2% for Carestart G6PD with a difference (95% CI) of 4.5 (1.6 to 7.4, p=0.003). The difference in sensitivity (95% CI) was 6.7 (-8.0 to 21.3, p=0.331). At the 70% threshold for Carestart G6PD there was evidence to suggest a difference in the sensitivity and specificity between the two tests. The sensitivity of Carestart G6PD was 56.5%, significantly lower than the 77.1% for G6PD Qualitative FST with an absolute difference (95% CI) of 20.6 (3.9 to 37.2, p=0.022). Whereas the specificity of G6PD

Qualitative FST was 93.6%, significantly lower than the 96.7% for Carestart G6PD with a difference (95% CI) of 3.1 (0.6 to 5.6, $p=0.018$).

Four studies compared Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST in the same population (Roca Feltrer 2004, Bancone 2015(b), Oo 2016 and Satyagraha 2016) at the 30% threshold value. The summary points estimated by the bivariate model is presented in [figure 7](#). There was no evidence to suggest a difference in the sensitivity and specificity between the two brands ([Table 6](#)). The absolute difference in sensitivity (95% CI) and specificity (95% CI) was -1.4 (-4.5, 1.8), and -1.0 (-3.9, 2.0), respectively.

Figure 7 – Summary points using the bivariate model for direct comparison of Carestart G6PD (Qualitative) and G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative) at 30% threshold (including Roca Feltrer 2004, Oo 2016, Bancone 2015(b) and Satyagraha 2016). Scale of individual study points is based on sample size.

LaRue 2014 directly compared the accuracy of G6PD Qualitative FST and BinaxNOW G6PD at the 30% threshold value. The difference in sensitivity was 0.0 between the two brands ([Table 7](#)), with both tests having a sensitivity of 100.0%. There was evidence to suggest a difference in the specificity with an absolute difference (95% CI) of 3.1 (0.3 to 5.8, $p=0.032$).

Indirect comparisons between qualitative tests at the 30% threshold

Indirect comparisons between test brands for qualitative and quantitative near patient G6PD tests at the 30% and 70% threshold

Sensitivities and specificities were derived from studies evaluating qualitative tests at threshold values of 30% and 70%, (Figure 6 and 7). The sensitivity of Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST tests varied between studies from 62% to 100% and from 93% to 100%, respectively at the 30% threshold. The specificity of Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST varied between studies from

68% to 100% and from 75% to 99%, respectively at the 30% threshold. No significant differences in summary sensitivities and specificities were found between Carestart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST.

Quantitative near patient G6PD tests

For quantitative G6PD tests we provide diagnostic accuracy analyses based on the adjusted male median reference for both the Carestart G6PD biosensor and Standard G6PD biosensor. For the Standard G6PD biosensor reference thresholds based on manufacturer cutoffs are also considered. In addition to the 30% and 70% cutoffs, a female only analysis is also provided for the 30-70% cutoffs due to the implications of diagnostic accuracy for G6PD in heterozygous females.

Pooled analyses for quantitative near patient G6PD tests

Pooled analysis of quantitative tests at the 30% threshold by test brands using the adjusted male median

Pooled analyses was performed on the Carestart G6PD Biosensor and Standard G6PD biosensor for the 30% threshold (Figure 8). Encompassing a total of 6 study arms and 4613 participants, the sensitivity of the Standard G6PD biosensor at a 30% cutoff was 89.1 (68.2 – 96.9%) and specificity of 99.6 (99.2 – 99.8%). We noted a wide variation in the sensitivity reported with the Carestart G6PD Biosensor (6 study arms and 2002 total participant samples) at this threshold and the pooled sensitivity was noted at 15.9% (4.7 – 42.0%). The pooled specificity for this test at a 30% threshold was 98.9% (95.9 – 99.7%) (Table 3)

Pooled analysis of quantitative tests at the 70% threshold by test brands using the adjusted male median

For the Standard G6PD test at the 70% threshold, 6 study arms comprising of 4613 patient samples reported data. The cumulative sensitivity was 86.7% (72.8 – 94.0%) and specificity 95.7% (92.7 – 97.5%). In comparison for the Carestart G6PD Biosensor, the cumulative sensitivity was noted at 58.4%(45.5 – 70.2) and specificity at 90.5% (80.2 – 95.8%) (Table 3).

Carestart G6PD Biosensor 30% AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Hamid 2018 CareStart AMM	0	11	2	200	0.00 [0.00, 0.84]	0.95 [0.91, 0.97]
Wepelmann 2017 CareStart AMM	1	1	33	308	0.03 [0.00, 0.15]	1.00 [0.98, 1.00]
Bancone 2018 Carestart G6PD AMM	2	0	46	102	0.04 [0.01, 0.14]	1.00 [0.96, 1.00]
Ley 2017 CareStart AMM	17	12	72	893	0.19 [0.12, 0.29]	0.99 [0.98, 0.99]
Alam 2018 CareStart AMM	14	0	18	120	0.44 [0.26, 0.62]	1.00 [0.97, 1.00]
Aung 2023 CareStart AMM	12	7	8	123	0.60 [0.36, 0.81]	0.95 [0.89, 0.98]

Carestart G6PD Biosensor 70% AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Ley 2017 CareStart AMM	96	71	126	701	0.43 [0.37, 0.50]	0.91 [0.89, 0.93]
Wepelmann 2017 CareStart AMM	44	16	50	233	0.47 [0.36, 0.57]	0.94 [0.90, 0.96]
Alam 2018 CareStart AMM	30	0	33	89	0.48 [0.35, 0.61]	1.00 [0.96, 1.00]
Hamid 2018 CareStart AMM	9	42	6	156	0.60 [0.32, 0.84]	0.79 [0.72, 0.84]
Aung 2023 CareStart AMM	22	29	10	89	0.69 [0.50, 0.84]	0.75 [0.67, 0.83]
Bancone 2018 Carestart G6PD AMM	67	7	17	59	0.80 [0.70, 0.88]	0.89 [0.79, 0.96]

Standard G6PD Biosensor 30% AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia venous	6	0	6	1003	0.50 [0.21, 0.79]	1.00 [1.00, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia capillary	8	0	4	997	0.67 [0.35, 0.90]	1.00 [1.00, 1.00]
Pal 2021 AMM Venous	37	3	15	651	0.71 [0.57, 0.83]	1.00 [0.99, 1.00]
Pal 2021 AMM Capillary	35	1	13	572	0.73 [0.58, 0.85]	1.00 [0.99, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Venous	21	5	5	829	0.81 [0.61, 0.93]	0.99 [0.99, 1.00]
Zobrist 2021 AMM Venous	46	3	9	1594	0.84 [0.71, 0.92]	1.00 [0.99, 1.00]
Zobrist 2021 AMM capillary	50	7	8	1620	0.86 [0.75, 0.94]	1.00 [0.99, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Capillary	24	6	3	856	0.89 [0.71, 0.98]	0.99 [0.98, 1.00]
Alam 2018 SG6PD AMM Venous	29	1	1	77	0.97 [0.83, 1.00]	0.99 [0.93, 1.00]
Pal 2018 AMM	25	1	0	184	1.00 [0.86, 1.00]	0.99 [0.97, 1.00]
Alam 2018 S6PD AMM Capillary	30	0	0	78	1.00 [0.88, 1.00]	1.00 [0.95, 1.00]

Standard G6PD Biosensor 70% AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia capillary	21	16	26	946	0.45 [0.30, 0.60]	0.98 [0.97, 0.99]
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia venous	21	15	26	953	0.45 [0.30, 0.60]	0.98 [0.97, 0.99]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Venous	48	54	11	747	0.81 [0.69, 0.90]	0.93 [0.91, 0.95]
Alam 2018 S6PD AMM Capillary	44	3	8	53	0.85 [0.72, 0.93]	0.95 [0.85, 0.99]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Capillary	51	65	9	764	0.85 [0.73, 0.93]	0.92 [0.90, 0.94]
Alam 2018 SG6PD AMM Venous	45	0	7	56	0.87 [0.74, 0.94]	1.00 [0.94, 1.00]
Pal 2021 AMM Capillary	61	20	7	533	0.90 [0.80, 0.96]	0.96 [0.94, 0.98]
Pal 2021 AMM Venous	116	13	13	564	0.90 [0.83, 0.95]	0.98 [0.96, 0.99]
Pal 2018 AMM	35	15	3	157	0.92 [0.79, 0.98]	0.91 [0.86, 0.95]
Zobrist 2021 AMM capillary	98	90	4	1493	0.96 [0.90, 0.99]	0.94 [0.93, 0.95]
Zobrist 2021 AMM Venous	95	57	1	1499	0.99 [0.94, 1.00]	0.96 [0.95, 0.97]

Figure 8 – Forest plots for quantitative G6PD tests at 30% and 70% thresholds

Pooled analysis for females of quantitative tests at the 30 - 70% threshold by test brands using the adjusted male median

For female participants, pooled analysis at the 30 – 70% threshold a high variability among studies was noted for both quantitative tests (Figure 9). Overall sensitivity for the Standard G6PD biosensor at the 30- 70% threshold was 66.4%(50.4 – 79.4%) and specificity was 95.1%(92.2 - 96.9%) for a total of 2226 participants. For the Carestart G6PD biosensor pooled sensitivity at this threshold was 32.8%(15.9 – 55.8%) and specificity was 89.8%(77.9 – 95.7%), for a total of 1029 participants.

Carestart G6PD Biosensor 30 - 70% (F) AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Alam 2018 CareStart AMM	2	0	28	70	0.07 [0.01, 0.22]	1.00 [0.95, 1.00]
Aung 2023 CareStart AMM	1	7	4	14	0.20 [0.01, 0.72]	0.67 [0.43, 0.85]
Ley 2017 CareStart AMM	18	38	64	433	0.22 [0.14, 0.32]	0.92 [0.89, 0.94]
Wepelmann 2017 CareStart AMM	12	8	24	120	0.33 [0.19, 0.51]	0.94 [0.88, 0.97]
Hamid 2018 CareStart AMM	5	12	4	84	0.56 [0.21, 0.86]	0.88 [0.79, 0.93]
Bancone 2018 Carestart G6PD AMM	17	17	7	40	0.71 [0.49, 0.87]	0.70 [0.57, 0.82]

Standard G6PD Biosensor 30 - 70% (F) AMM

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Pal 2018 AMM	0	12	2	100	0.00 [0.00, 0.84]	0.89 [0.82, 0.94]
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia capillary	7	8	12	442	0.37 [0.16, 0.62]	0.98 [0.97, 0.99]
Adissu 2023 AMM Ethiopia venous	7	8	12	448	0.37 [0.16, 0.62]	0.98 [0.97, 0.99]
Alam 2018 S6PD AMM Capillary	14	2	7	47	0.67 [0.43, 0.85]	0.96 [0.86, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Venous	11	31	5	463	0.69 [0.41, 0.89]	0.94 [0.91, 0.96]
Pal 2021 AMM Capillary	7	11	3	307	0.70 [0.35, 0.93]	0.97 [0.94, 0.98]
Alam 2018 SG6PD AMM Venous	14	0	6	49	0.70 [0.46, 0.88]	1.00 [0.93, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 AMM India Capillary	12	38	4	477	0.75 [0.48, 0.93]	0.93 [0.90, 0.95]
Pal 2021 AMM Venous	8	4	2	311	0.80 [0.44, 0.97]	0.99 [0.97, 1.00]
Zobrist 2021 AMM capillary	9	46	1	652	0.90 [0.55, 1.00]	0.93 [0.91, 0.95]
Zobrist 2021 AMM Venous	9	35	0	643	1.00 [0.66, 1.00]	0.95 [0.93, 0.96]

Figure 9 - Pooled analysis for quantitative tests using the AMM thresholds at the 30-70% range

Pooled analysis for all quantitative tests at 30% and 70%, including data for female participants at a 30-70% threshold are presented in [table 9](#). When considering all quantitative tests the pooled sensitivity at a 30% threshold was 47.6% (17.8 – 79.2%), but with a wide variation. The sensitivity at 70% was 91.8% (80.5 – 96.8%). Specificities at 30 and 70% cutoffs were 98.1% (96.4 – 99%) and 92.3% (86.3 – 95.8%) respectively ([Table 9](#)). When combining all data from quantitative tests at the 70% threshold the pooled sensitivity was 87.8% (17.2 – 99.6%) and specificity 98.1% (96.5 – 99.0%). For female participants at the 30- 70% threshold sensitivity and specificity was noted at 45.5% (26.5- 65.9%) and 92.8% (87.0 – 96.1%). ([Table 9](#))

Manufacturer based thresholds for Standard G6PD biosensor, 30, 70, 30 – 70 (female only) analysis

For the Standard G6PD biosensor a supplementary analysis was performed using manufacturer based reference points ([Figure 10, table 10](#)). The overall sensitivity and specificity for 30% and 70% thresholds was higher when calculated from manufacturer specifications. Sensitivity at the 30% threshold was 100%(98.2 – 100%) and specificity was 97.0% (96.5 – 97.5%). Sensitivity at the 70% threshold was 91.4% (75.5 – 97.4%) and specificity was 93.7% (85.8 – 97.4%).

For female participants, sensitivity at a 30-70% range was 52.9% (28.9 – 75.7%) and specificity was 94.7% (86.3 – 98.0%). A wide variability in diagnostic accuracy metrics was noted at this threshold.

Standard G6PD Biosensor 30% Manu.

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Alam 2018 S6PD Manufac Capillary	30	9	0	69	1.00 [0.88, 1.00]	0.88 [0.79, 0.95]
Alam 2018 SG6PD Manufac. Venous	30	8	0	70	1.00 [0.88, 1.00]	0.90 [0.81, 0.95]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Venous	52	56	0	598	1.00 [0.93, 1.00]	0.91 [0.89, 0.93]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Capillary	27	21	0	841	1.00 [0.87, 1.00]	0.98 [0.96, 0.98]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Venous	26	20	0	814	1.00 [0.87, 1.00]	0.98 [0.96, 0.99]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Capillary	58	37	0	1590	1.00 [0.94, 1.00]	0.98 [0.97, 0.98]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Capillary	48	13	0	560	1.00 [0.93, 1.00]	0.98 [0.96, 0.99]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Venous	55	23	0	1574	1.00 [0.94, 1.00]	0.99 [0.98, 0.99]
Pal 2018 Manufac.	25	2	0	183	1.00 [0.86, 1.00]	0.99 [0.96, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac. Capillary	12	7	0	990	1.00 [0.74, 1.00]	0.99 [0.99, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac Venous	12	6	0	997	1.00 [0.74, 1.00]	0.99 [0.99, 1.00]

Standard G6PD Biosensor 70% Manu.

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac Venous	25	34	22	934	0.53 [0.38, 0.68]	0.96 [0.95, 0.98]
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac. Capillary	27	53	20	909	0.57 [0.42, 0.72]	0.94 [0.93, 0.96]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Capillary	44	37	16	792	0.73 [0.60, 0.84]	0.96 [0.94, 0.97]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Venous	45	46	14	755	0.76 [0.63, 0.86]	0.94 [0.92, 0.96]
Alam 2018 SG6PD Manufac. Venous	46	4	6	52	0.88 [0.77, 0.96]	0.93 [0.83, 0.98]
Pal 2018 Manufac.	34	0	4	172	0.89 [0.75, 0.97]	1.00 [0.98, 1.00]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Capillary	64	57	4	496	0.94 [0.86, 0.98]	0.90 [0.87, 0.92]
Alam 2018 S6PD Manufac Capillary	50	13	2	43	0.96 [0.87, 1.00]	0.77 [0.64, 0.87]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Capillary	101	160	3	1421	0.97 [0.92, 0.99]	0.90 [0.88, 0.91]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Venous	127	79	2	498	0.98 [0.95, 1.00]	0.86 [0.83, 0.89]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Venous	96	74	0	1482	1.00 [0.96, 1.00]	0.95 [0.94, 0.96]

Standard G6PD Biosensor 30 - 70% (F) Manu.

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Pal 2018 Manufac.	0	0	3	134	0.00 [0.00, 0.71]	1.00 [0.97, 1.00]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Capillary	5	14	10	494	0.33 [0.12, 0.62]	0.97 [0.95, 0.98]
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac Venous	5	17	9	439	0.36 [0.13, 0.65]	0.96 [0.94, 0.98]
Adissu 2023 India Manufac. Venous	7	18	8	469	0.47 [0.21, 0.73]	0.96 [0.94, 0.98]
Adissu 2023 Ethiopia Manufac. Capillary	8	19	9	427	0.47 [0.23, 0.72]	0.96 [0.93, 0.97]
Alam 2018 SG6PD Manufac. Venous	8	4	5	45	0.62 [0.32, 0.86]	0.92 [0.80, 0.98]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Capillary	3	32	1	284	0.75 [0.19, 0.99]	0.90 [0.86, 0.93]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Capillary	4	85	1	608	0.80 [0.28, 0.99]	0.88 [0.85, 0.90]
Alam 2018 S6PD Manufac Capillary	10	11	2	38	0.83 [0.52, 0.98]	0.78 [0.63, 0.88]
Pal 2021 Manufac. Venous	5	37	1	274	0.83 [0.36, 1.00]	0.88 [0.84, 0.91]
Zobrist 2021 Manufac. Venous	4	42	0	633	1.00 [0.40, 1.00]	0.94 [0.92, 0.95]

Figure 10 - Pooled analysis for Standard G6PD biosensor tests using manufacturer thresholds

Classification plots for Standard G6PD biosensor and Carestart G6PD biosensor

As a supplementary analysis to the sensitivity and specificity data presented above for the quantitative G6PD tests we also provide classification plots for blood type, AMM and manufacturer thresholds wherever possible. In the plots that follow, represented on the Y-axis is the G6PD activity by Spectrophotometer normalised to the 100% reported in each study. On the X-axis is the classification of G6PD status by index test in females (F, upper pane) and males (M, lower panes). All graphs are capped at 200% G6PD activity by spectrophotometer to facilitate visualization of the 30% and 70% thresholds.

Direct and Indirect comparisons between quantitative near patient G6PD tests

Direct comparisons between test brands for quantitative near patient G6PD tests

None of the included studies included in this review performed a direct comparative analysis between quantitative near patient G6PD tests

Indirect comparative analyses between quantitative near patient G6PD tests at the 30% threshold using the adjusted male median as reference

An indirect comparative analysis was not undertaken with Carestart G6PD Biosensor by AccessBio and Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor at a threshold of 30% due to extremely large and no variability between studies in the sensitivity, respectively.

Indirect comparative analysis between quantitative tests at the 70% threshold using the adjusted male median as reference

The sensitivity observed in studies evaluating the Standard G6PD biosensor at the 70% threshold varied from 45% to 99%. (Table 11) The specificity for the same test brand at the 70% threshold varied between 91% to 100%. At the same threshold the variation in sensitivity and specificity for the Carestart G6PD biosensor was between 43% and 80%, and 75% to 94% respectively. A significant difference in sensitivity was noted between the Standard G6PD biosensor and Carestart G6PD Biosensor at a 70% threshold (86.3% vs 59.2%; $p = 0.005$). However, there was no statistical significance demonstrated in the two tests when considering specificity.

Direct and Indirect comparisons between qualitative and quantitative near patient G6PD tests

None of the studies included in this review performed direct comparative analyses between qualitative and quantitative G6PD tests.

Indirect comparative analyses between qualitative and quantitative test brands at the 30 and 70% thresholds (Table 12 and 13)

There was evidence to suggest significantly higher specificity for the quantitative Standard G6PD biosensor compared to the qualitative Carestart G6PD at a 30% threshold. (99.7%, 95% CI 99.1 – 99.9 vs 96.3%; 95% CI – 93.8% - 97.9%, $p = 0.001$). However, there was no significant difference in the sensitivity of the two tests. Similar findings were noted when comparing the Standard G6PD biosensor to the G6PD qualitative FST, with the Standard G6PD biosensor recording a significantly higher specificity ($p = 0.008$).

At the 70% threshold the quantitative Standard G6PD biosensor had a significantly higher sensitivity compared to the qualitative Carestart G6PD (86.3% 95% CI – 74.7% - 93.0%, vs 52.5, CI 33.7 – 70.5%, $p = 0.002$), and a trend to significance compared to the G6PD qualitative FST (86.3% 95% CI – 74.7% - 93.0% vs. 77.8%, 95% CI – 61.5 – 88.5%, $p = 0.310$). No significant differences were noted between these test when considering the specificity metrics.

A statistically significant difference was noted in the comparative specificity between the quantitative Carestart G6PD Biosensor and the qualitative Carestart G6PD at the 70% threshold (90.4%, CI – 82.3 – 95% vs 97.1, 95% CI – 95.0 – 98.6%). No significant differences were noted between the Carestart G6PD biosensor and the G6PD qualitative FST at this threshold.

Indirect comparisons at the 30% and 70% thresholds comparing qualitative and quantitative G6PD tests

A threshold value of 30% contained both quantitative and qualitative tests, however an indirect comparative analysis was not undertaken due to extremely large variability in the sensitivity of quantitative tests at this threshold.

Sensitivities and specificities were derived from studies reporting on qualitative tests and quantitative tests at the threshold value of 70% (Figure 7). No significant difference in summary sensitivities were found between quantitative tests (73.7%, 95% CI: 50.7 – 85.5%) and qualitative tests (70.6%, 95% CI: 46.9, 86.7) (Table 14). No significant differences in summary specificities were found between quantitative tests (93.6%, 95% CI: 89.1, 96.3) and qualitative tests (94.9%, 95% CI: 89.6 to 97.6%).

Investigations of heterogeneity

Heterogeneity analysis was limited number of studies in each category considered. However, a limited analysis was possible for blood type for the Standard G6PD biosensor for 30 and 70% thresholds. It was not possible to extend this analysis to the 30 – 70% threshold for female participants due to high variability between studies.

Blood type based heterogeneity analysis for the Standard G6PD biosensor

We performed a heterogeneity analysis for capillary vs venous blood for the Standard G6PD biosensor (Tables 14 and 15) . A total of 6 study arms evaluated venous blood with a total number of 4551 participants. Five study arms evaluated capillary blood with a total of 4321 participants.

Considering reference thresholds based on the adjusted male median, there was no statistically significant difference in either the sensitivity or specificity for venous vs capillary blood for the 30%, 70% thresholds. Heterogeneity analysis for blood type was not possible for the female only subgroup due to high variability between studies.

Considering reference thresholds based on the adjusted male median, there was no statistically significant difference in either the sensitivity or specificity for venous vs capillary blood for the 30%, 70% thresholds.

Sensitivity analyses

Where sufficient data was available, a sensitivity analysis was undertaken at each QUADAS-2 domain by excluding studies that yielded a high or an unclear risk of bias following the QUADAS assessment (Table 16 – 21). After excluding the studies, all analyses for each specific QUADAS-2 domain did not result in a change in both statistical significance and direction of the results from the main analysis.

Discussion

Here we present data on the diagnostic accuracy of near patient G6PD tests. Despite the fact that several studies reported multiple thresholds, we restricted this review to the clinically relevant thresholds used to inform use of primaquine and tafenoquine in the radical cure and prophylaxis of *P. vivax* and *ovale* malaria. The 30% threshold that is currently used to guide primaquine radical cure (von Seidlein et al., 2013) and the 70% cutoff which is proposed as threshold for tafenoquine treatment to ensure safe use in females with intermediate activity and also more recently to inform safe use of short course high dose 7-day regimen of primaquine (LaRue et al., 2014; Rueangwearayut et al., 2017; Thriemer et al., 2023).

An important consideration in reporting G6PD results the reference G6PD activity used to calculate these thresholds. In this review we took the approach of harmonizing the reference threshold to the adjusted male median value (AMM). The use of AMM was initially suggested to decrease variability in the definition of “G6PD normal” by excluding males with very low activity (<10%) who would be deficient. This approach would be feasible even in settings where genotyping is not done or common mutations are not known. However, it is also now apparent that in many G6PD mutations, residual enzymatic activity in males is often higher than 10% and the use of whole blood specimens rather than white blood cells depleted samples (Beutler et al., 1977) for spectrophotometric analysis tends to increase detected activity in deficient samples ; therefore, the AMM calculated in this way includes some deficient males. With the aforementioned limitations, the AMM still provides an excellent tool for harmonization of result reporting and comparisons across index tests.

In the same way, thresholds for quantitative near patient test can be calculated from the 100% male median or they can be optimized by using statistical methods (such as AUC of the ROC curve) to maximize test performance compared to reference spectrophotometry. For the Standard G6PD biosensor, manufacturer's thresholds (obtained by the manufacturer during evaluation studies) were also included in the analyses presented.

The performance of near patient G6PD tests is presented as sensitivity and specificity, which are both important to understand how well a test identifies G6PD deficient and intermediate subjects who should not be taking standard primaquine or tafenoquine regimens and how often valuable treatment options are withheld from individuals who could be safely treated. In the context of vivax radical cure with 8-aminoquinolines, G6PD tests with high sensitivity are crucial for individuals' treatment safety, while high specificity of tests is required for efficacy treatment and, at population for impact malaria vivax transmission and elimination.

We have found an abundance of evaluation studies for qualitative tests which is unmatched by quantitative tests they have been developed fairly recently; therefore, some pooled analyses could only be only carried out for the qualitative tests.

Performance at the 30% threshold

When evaluating qualitative POC tests for this threshold, the Carestart G6PD and Qualitative FST were the most used test and showed excellent performance with pooled sensitivity and specificity close or over 95%. Performance of the BinaxNow G6PD and WST8/1-methoxy PMS assay was tested in fewer studies and was high in BinaxNow and lower in WST8/1-methoxy PMS assay. In the studies where tests were compared directly, there was no statistically significant difference when studies were combined using a bivariate model between the CareStart G6PD and Qualitative FST .The WST-8 had significantly inferior sensitivity, but higher specificity compared to the Qualitative FST in direct comparisons. This analysis also revealed higher specificity of the BinaxNow compared to the FST.

Considering performance of the quantitative tests using the adjusted male median for Carestart G6PD at a 30% threshold a very low sensitivity was noted putting malaria patients at potentially great risk of haemolysis. Comparatively better sensitivity was noted with the standard G6PD biosensor at this threshold but was still only close to 48%. Of note, analysis of Standard G6PD test at this threshold using the manufacturer's cut-off of 4IU/gHb showed excellent sensitivity but lower specificity (showing that this is a conservative threshold that optimizes safety). A manufacturer threshold does not exist for the Carestart G6PD biosensor, hence no comparative analyses were possible.

We could not perform comparative statistical analyses comparing the 2 quantitative G6PD tests, CareStart G6PD biosensor and Standard G6PD biosensor at a 30% threshold due to lack of studies performing direct comparison and indirect comparison being affected by incompatible variability metrics between study arms. However, meta-analysis at this threshold suggested that Carestart biosensor had inferior performance compared to the Standard G6PD test albeit without statistical significance.

Performance at 70% threshold

Some studies reported sensitivity and specificity metrics for 70% cutoff in qualitative tests, which were markedly low in most cases and should be interpreted with caution given that qualitative tests are not usually built to identify multiple thresholds. Overall, sensitivity of qualitative tests at the 70% threshold was poor with the highest observed in the FST with 73.8%.

Indirect comparisons between the Standard G6PD Biosensor and Carestart G6PD biosensor showed superior sensitivity of the former. Specificity of the Standard G6PD biosensor was also higher but without statistical significance.

Indirect comparisons between qualitative and quantitative tests at this threshold showed as expected that the sensitivity of Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor was significantly greater than CareStart G6PD and G6PD Qualitative FST. No significant differences in summary specificities were found between these tests, however we did note statistical significance when data from the CareStart G6PD biosensor were removed. Nevertheless, these comparative analyses between qualitative and quantitative tests need to be interpreted with caution due to the inherent differences in test mechanisms and interpretation of these tests.

Performance at 30-70% threshold and in females only

In scenarios where qualitative tests are available and usually cheaper than quantitative tests, a cost-saving approach to testing G6PD for malaria treatment could be to use qualitative testing in males and reserve the quantitative testing to females. Therefore, we have provided an analysis of quantitative tests performance for the intermediate phenotype (30-70% activity) in females only. Results in the Carestart test are in line with what observed at the 30% and 70% thresholds, i.e. poor performance overall with low sensitivity and variable specificity. For the Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor, results in intermediate females show good performance using the AMM but only fair performance using the manufacturer's thresholds which possibly reflects the conservative nature of the 30% threshold and optimization of safety.

Risk of bias and heterogeneity analyses

We considered studies with non – random sampling as high risk of bias as per the QUADAS2. However pragmatically when considering G6PD testing the impact of randomization of patient recruitment may not have the same consequences compared to other diagnostic tests, as long as the evaluation studies include the whole range of G6PD activities.

The heterogeneity analyses were extremely limited in this review due to limited number of studies and insufficient heterogeneity between them.

Limitations

Although pre-specified in the protocol we could not conduct a robust male vs female comparative analysis due to inconsistent reporting of data based on gender across studies. We also did not compare the diagnostic accuracy of these tests in malaria patients compared to healthy volunteers due to the constraints in modelling the impact of physiological disturbances on G6PD activity and test performance in patients infected with malaria.

While technical performance is based the analyzed features, overall suitability of a test depends from other characteristics too, including the test specifics (such as storage and testing temperature and humidity stability; usability; price) and the context in which the test will be used. This analysis was beyond the scope of this review.

Key Conclusions

- Considering the 30% threshold qualitative and quantitative tests have equivalent diagnostic accuracy
- Quantitative tests are required for evaluation of G6PD activity at the 70% threshold

- When considering qualitative tests, the diagnostic performance of the Carestart G6PD and FST tests have superior performance compared to the BinaxNOW and WST – 8 tests
- The Standard G6PD biosensor showed superior and more consistent sensitivity and specificity metrics compared to the Carestart G6PD biosensor at the 30% threshold

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Appendix 1

Ovid MEDLINE search strategy

Database: Ovid MEDLINE and In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations <1946 to present

- 1 exp Glucosephosphate Dehydrogenase Deficiency/
- 2 ((glucose-6-phosphate-dehydrogenas* or glucose-phosphate-dehydrogenas* or G6PD or G-6-P-D or G-6-PD or GPD) adj3 (deficien* or lack)).tw. (4388)
- 3 (Glucosephosphate Dehydrogenase/ or (glucose-6-phosphate-dehydrogenas* or glucose-phosphate-dehydrogenas* or G6PD or G-6-P-D or G-6-PD or GPD).mp.) adj3 ((malaria* or Plasmodium or ovale or anemia or anaemia or hemolysis or antimalaria* or primaquine or tafenoquine).mp. or (Anemia, Sickle Cell/ or Sickle Cell Trait/))
- 4 1 or 2 or 3
- 5 qualitative test*.tw.
- 6 (fluorescent spot test* or FST).tw.
- 7 (diagnos* adj3 (assay* or test*)).tw,kf.
- 8 rapid diagnostic test*.tw,kf.
- 9 RDT*.tw,kf.
- 10 CareStart*.tw,kf.
- 11 BinaxNOW*.tw,kf.
- 12 exp Reagent Kits, Diagnostic/
- 13 G6PD-test*.tw,kf.
- 14 *Point-of-Care Systems/
- 15 *Point-of-Care Testing/
- 16 Diagnostic Tests, Routine/
- 17 *Clinical Chemistry Tests/
- 18 Clinical Enzyme Tests/
- 19 point of care.tw.
- 20 Histochemistry/
- 21 Histochemistry.tw.
- 22 Spectrophotometry/
- 23 spectrophotometr*.tw.
- 24 Sequence Analysis, DNA/
- 25 DNA sequenc*.tw.
- 26 Polymerase Chain Reaction/

27 ("Polymerase Chain Reaction" or PCR).tw.

28 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22
or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27

29 4 and 28

Table 1: Summary sensitivity and sensitivity of the qualitative tests by test brand and threshold								
Test and threshold	Studies	Participants	Cases	Pooled sensitivity % (95% CI)	Pooled specificity % (95% CI)	Numbers in a cohort of 1,000 patients tested (95% CI)		
						Prevalence of 5%	Prevalence of 10%	Prevalence of 20%
Carestart G6PD								
30%	15	9552	943	94.8 (89.3, 97.6)	96.4 (93.4, 98.1)	TP=47 (45, 49) FP=34 (18, 63) FN=3 (1, 5) TN=916 (887, 932)	TP=95 (89, 98) FP=32 (17, 59) FN=5 (2, 11) TN=868 (841, 883)	TP=190 (179, 195) FP=29 (15, 53) FN=10 (5, 21) TN=771 (747, 785)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Brito 2016, Kim 2011, Espino 2016, Albsheer 2021, Von Fricken 2014, Bancone 2015, Roh 2016, Wojnarski 2020, Henriques 2018, Satyagraha 2016, Oo 2016, Abdul Ghani 2016, Adu Gyasi 2015, Roca – Feltrer 2014 were used for this meta-analysis Bancone 2015(a) Espino 2016(c) excluded from meta-analysis, because Bancone 2015 (a) and (b) use the same participants, as do Espino 2016 (b) and (c). Difference between four studies is that Bancone 2015 (a) and Espino 2016 (c) uses capillary blood, and Bancone 2015(b) Espino 2016(b) uses venous blood samples. Bancone 2015(a) Espino 2016(c) were excluded, due to majority of studies using venous blood sample in the meta-analysis for this test. Adu-Gyasi 2015 (b) and Adu-Gyasi 2015 (c) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Adu-Gyasi 2015 (a), (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the three studies is that (a) consists of 205 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD, (b) consists of 119 male participants assessed by CareStart G6PD and (c) consists of 86 female participants assessed by CareStart G6PD. Espino 2016 (a) was chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. Of these studies Adu Gyasi 2015, Alam 2018, Albsheer 2021, Bancone 2015, Kiesling 2018 and Pal 2018 were rated high risk of bias with regard to patient selection due to non – random sampling Of these studies Bancone 2015, Oo 2016 and Espino 2016 had concerns regarding applicability of the index test as these were not performed in the near patient setting 								
70%	5	2653	518	52.5 (35.4, 69.1)	97.1 (94.1, 98.6)	TP=26 (18, 35) FP=28 (13, 56) FN=24 (15, 32) TN=922 (894, 937)	TP=53 (35, 69) FP=26 (13, 53) FN=47 (31, 65) TN=874 (847, 887)	TP=105 (71, 138) FP=23 (11, 47) FN=95 (62, 129) TN=777 (753, 789)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Albsheer 2021, Espino 2016, Henriques 2018, Satyagraha 2016 and Henriques 2018 were used for this meta-analysis Espino 2016(c) excluded from meta-analysis, Espino 2016 (b) and (c) use the same participants. Difference between two studies is that Espino 2016 (c) uses capillary blood and Espino 2016(b) uses venous blood samples. Espino 2016(c) was excluded, due to majority of studies using venous blood sample in the meta-analysis for this test. Concerns on risk of bias and applicability are summarized under data for the 30% threshold 								

BinaxNOW G6PD								
30%	2	234	24	+	+	-	-	-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Kuwahata 2010 and La Rue 2014 was included in this meta-analysis. Kuwahata 2010 consisted of 20 participants of which 6 were identified with cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the above test was 100.0 (54.1, 100.0) and 100.0 (76.8, 100.0) respectively. LaRue 2014 consisted of 214 participants of which 18 were identified as cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the above test was 100.0% (81.5, 100.0) and 99.5% (97.2, 100.0), respectively. Both studies had concerns on applicability as the index test was not performed in the near patient setting 								
G6PD Qualitative FST								
30%	9	5150	466	98.1 (96.3, 99.0)	95.4 (91.6, 97.6)	TP=49 (48, 50) FP=44 (23, 80) FN=1 (1, 2) TN=906 (870, 927)	TP=98 (96, 99) FP=41 (22, 76) FN=2 (1, 4) TN=859 (824, 878)	TP=196 (193, 198) FP=37 (19, 67) FN=4 (2, 7) TN=763 (733, 781)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Satyagraha 2016, Bancone 2015, Espino 2016, Henriques 2018, Oo 2016, La Rue 2014, Roca – Feltrer 2014 and Sumalai 2021 was used in this meta – analysis Bancone 2015(a) excluded from meta-analysis, because Bancone 2015 (a) and (b) use the same participants. Difference between two studies are that (a) uses capillary blood and (b) uses venous blood samples. Bancone 2015(a) was excluded, due to majority of studies using venous blood sample in the meta-analysis for this test. Of the studies included Bancone 2015, Henriques 2018 were rated high risk of bias with regard to patient selection due to non – random sampling. Henriques 2018 had high risk of bias in the flow and timing domain Of the studies included Bancone 2015, Espino 2016, LaRue 2014 and Oo 2016 had concerns regarding applicability of the index test as these were not performed in the near patient setting 								
70%	5	2808	549	78.3 (58.2, 90.4)	95.4 (90.6, 97.8)	TP=39 (29, 45) FP=44 (21, 89) FN=11 (5, 21) TN=906 (861, 929)	TP=78 (58, 90) FP=41 (20, 85) FN=22 (10, 42) TN=859 (815, 880)	TP=157 (116, 181) FP=37 (18, 75) FN=43 (19, 84) TN=763 (725, 782)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Espino 2016, Satyagraha 2016, Henriques 2018 and Sumalai 2021 was used in this meta – analysis Concerns on risk of bias and applicability are summarized under data for the 30% threshold 								
WST8/1-methoxy PMS assay								
30%	3	1626	142	-	-	-	-	-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from Ley 2017, Kuwahata 2010 and Espino 2016 was used in this meta-analysis Ley 2017 (b) consisted of 985 participants of which 79 were identified with cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the above test was 62.0% (50.4, 72.7) and 97.8% (96.6, 98.6), respectively. 								

- Kuwahata 2010 consisted of 20 participants of which 6 were identified as cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the above test was 83.3% (35.9, 99.6) and 100.0% (76.8, 100.0), respectively.
- Espino 2016 (a) consisted of 621 participants of which 57 were identified as cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the above test was 84.2% (72.1, 92.5) and 98.2% (96.8, 99.1), respectively.
- Kuwahata 2010 was considered to have concerns of applicability as the index test was not performed in the near patient setting

70% (Espino 2016(a))	1	621	134	38.8 (30.5, 47.6)	98.8 (97.3, 99.5)	TP=19 (15, 24) FP=11 (5, 26) FN=31 (26, 35) TN=939 (924, 945)	TP=39 (31, 48) FP=11 (5, 24) FN=61 (52, 69) TN=889 (876, 895)	TP=78 (61, 95) FP=10 (4, 22) FN=122 (105, 139) TN=790 (778, 796)
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TP=True Positive, FP= False Positive, FN=False negative, TN=True negative

† pooled estimate not obtained due to small number of studies.

Threshold	Studies	Participants	Cases	Pooled sensitivity % (95% CI)	Pooled specificity % (95% CI)	Numbers in a cohort of 1,000 patients tested (95% CI)		
						Prevalence of 5%	Prevalence of 10%	Prevalence of 20%
30%	19	11456	1103	94.9 (89.4, 97.6)	96.2 (93.5, 97.8)	TP=47 (45, 49) FP=36 (21, 62) FN=3 (1, 5) TN=914 (888, 929)	TP=95 (89, 98) FP=34 (20, 58) FN=5 (2, 11) TN=866 (842, 880)	TP=190 (179, 195) FP=30 (18, 52) FN=10 (5, 21) TN=770 (748, 782)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Espino 2016 (b) and Espino 2016 (c) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Espino 2016 (a), (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the three studies is that (a) consists of 621 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST, (b) consists of 302 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD using venous blood samples and (c) consists of 302 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD using capillary blood samples. Espino 2016 (a) was chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. Henriques 2018 (b) and (d) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Henriques 2018 (a) and (b) use the same participants, and Henriques 2018 (c) and (d) use the same participants. Difference between (a) and (b) is that (a) consists of 505 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST and (b) consists of 498 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD enrolled in Cambodia. Difference between (c) and (d) is that (c) consists of 757 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST and (d) consists of 753 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD enrolled in Laos. Henriques 2018 (a) and (c) were chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. Bancone 2015(a) excluded from meta-analysis, because Bancone 2015 (a) and (b) use the same participants. Difference between two studies are that (a) uses capillary blood and (b) uses venous blood samples. Bancone 2015(a) was excluded, due to majority of studies using venous blood sample in the meta-analysis for this test. Adu-Gyasi 2015 (b) and Adu-Gyasi 2015 (c) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Adu-Gyasi 2015 (a), (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the three studies is that (a) consists of 205 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD, (b) consists of 119 male participants assessed by CareStart G6PD and (c) consists of 86 female participants assessed by CareStart G6PD. Espino 2016 (a) was chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. 								
70%	6	3298	683	70.9 (44.3, 88.1)	94.8 (90.3, 97.3)	TP=35 (22, 44) FP=49 (26, 92) FN=15 (6, 28) TN=901 (858, 924)	TP=71 (44, 88) FP=47 (24, 87) FN=29 (12, 56) TN=853 (813, 876)	TP=142 (89, 176) FP=42 (22, 78) FN=58 (24, 111) TN=758 (722, 778)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Espino 2016 (b) and Espino 2016 (c) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Espino 2016 (a), (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the three studies is that (a) consists of 621 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST, (b) consists of 302 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD using venous blood samples and (c) consists of 302 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD using capillary blood samples. Espino 2016 (a) was chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. Henriques 2018 (b) and (d) were excluded from meta-analysis, because Henriques 2018 (a) and (b) use the same participants, and Henriques 2018 (c) and (d) use the same participants. Difference between (a) and (b) is that (a) consists of 505 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST and (b) consists of 498 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD enrolled in Cambodia. Difference between (c) and (d) is that (c) consists of 757 participants assessed by G6PD Qualitative FST and (d) consists of 753 participants assessed by CareStart G6PD enrolled in Laos. Henriques 2018 (a) and (c) were chosen, due to having a more complete sample size. 								

TP=True Positive, FP= False Positive, FN=False negative, TN=True negative

* pooled estimate not obtained due to small number of studies.

Study	Threshold	Sensitivity (true positives/ cases) (%)		Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Specificity (true negatives/non-cases) (%)		Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value
		WST8/1-methoxy PMS	BinaxNOW G6PD		WST8/1-methoxy PMS	BinaxNOW G6PD	
Kuwahata 2010	30%	83.3 (5/6)	100.0 (6/6)	-16.7 (-46.5, 13.2), p=0.296	100.0 (14/14)	100.0 (14/14)	*

*unable to make direct comparison as specificity of both tests is 100.0%.

Study	Threshold	Sensitivity (true positives/ cases) (%)		Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Specificity (true negatives/non-cases) (%)		Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value
		WST8/1-methoxy PMS	G6PD Qualitative FST		WST8/1-methoxy PMS	G6PD Qualitative FST	
Espino 2016(a)	30%	84.2 (48/57)	96.5 (55/57)	-12.3 (-22.9, -1.7), p=0.026	98.2 (554/564)	95.2 (537/564)	3.0 (0.9, 5.1), p=0.005
	70%	38.8 (52/134)	55.2 (74/134)	-16.4 (-28.2, -4.6), p=0.007	98.8 (481/487)	98.4 (479/487)	0.4 (-1.1, 1.9), p=0.590

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value		Study: Satyagraha 2016	Carestart G6PD			
			10%	30%	60%	70%
		Sensitivity (true positives/ cases) (%)	100.0 (20/20)	96.7 (29/30)	72.9 (35/48)	56.5 (39/69)
		Specificity (true negatives/non-cases) (%)	93.7 (553/590)	95.2 (552/580)	96.1 (540/562)	96.7 (523/541)
G6PD Qualitative FST	10%	90.0 (18/20) 90.7 (535/590)	10.0 (-3.1, 23.1), p=0.147 3.1 (0.0, 6.1), p=0.051	6.7 (-8.0, 21.3), p=0.331 4.5 (1.6, 7.4), p=0.003	-	-
	30%	93.3 (28/30) 92.2 (535/580)	6.7 (-2.3, 15.6), p=0.239 1.5 (-1.4, 4.4), p=0.319	See results in Table 8	-	-
	60%	77.1 (37/48) 93.6 (526/562)	-	-	-4.2 (-21.5, 13.1), p=0.637 2.5 (-0.1, 5.1), p=0.059	-20.6 (-37.2, -3.9), p=0.022 3.1 (0.6, 5.6), p=0.018
	70%	60.9 (42/69) 94.3 (510/541)	-	-	12.0 (-5.0, 29.1), p=0.177 1.8 (-0.7, 4.3), p=0.159	-4.3 (-20.8, 12.1), p=0.604 2.4 (-0.1, 4.9), p=0.057

Table 6: Direct comparison between Carestart G6PD test (Qualitative) and G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative) test at 30% threshold

Study	Threshold	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)		Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)		Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value
		Carestart G6PD	G6PD Qualitative FST		Carestart G6PD	G6PD Qualitative FST	
Roca Feltrer 2014, Oo 2016, Satyagraha 2016, Bancone 2015(b)	30%	96.3 (92.9, 98.2) (211/219)	97.7 (94.6, 99.0) (214/219)	-1.4 (-4.5, 1.8), p=0.398	95.6 (92.5, 97.4) (2344/2479)	96.5 (94.1, 98.0) (2385/2479)	-1.0 (-3.9, 2.0), p=0.517

Bancone 2015(a) excluded from analysis, because Bancone 2015 (a) and (b) use the same participants. Difference between two studies are that (a) uses capillary blood and (b) uses venous blood samples. Bancone 2015(a) was excluded, due to majority of studies using venous blood sample in the meta-analysis for this test.

Table 7: Direct comparison between BinaxNOW G6PD test (Qualitative) and G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative) at 30% threshold

Study	Threshold	Sensitivity (true positives/ cases) (%)		Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Specificity (true negatives/non-cases) (%)		Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value
		G6PD Qualitative FST	BinaxNOW G6PD		G6PD Qualitative FST	BinaxNOW G6PD	
LaRue 2014	30%	100.0 (18/18)	100.0 (18/18)	*	96.4 (189/196)	99.5 (195/196)	-3.1 (-5.8, -0.3), p=0.032

*unable to make direct comparison as sensitivity of both tests is 100.0%.

Table 8 Summary sensitivity and sensitivity of the quantitative tests by test brand and threshold								
Test and threshold	Studies	Participants	Cases	Pooled sensitivity % (95% CI)	Pooled specificity % (95% CI)	Numbers in a cohort of 1,000 patients tested (95% CI)		
						Prevalence of 5%	Prevalence of 10%	Prevalence of 20%
Carestart G6PD Biosensor by AccessBio								
30% AMM	6	2002	225	15.9 (4.7, 42.0) †	98.9 (95.9, 99.7)	TP=8 (2, 21) FP=10 (3, 39) FN=42 (29, 48) TN=940 (911, 947)	TP=16 (5, 42) FP=10 (3, 37) FN=84 (58, 95) TN=890 (863, 897)	TP=32 (9, 84) FP=9 (2, 33) FN=168 (116, 191) TN=791 (767, 798)
70% AMM	6	2002	510	58.4 (45.5, 70.2)	90.5 (80.2, 95.8)	TP=29 (23, 35) FP=90 (40, 188) FN=21 (15, 27) TN=860 (762, 910)	TP=58 (46, 70) FP=85 (38, 178) FN=42 (30, 54) TN=815 (722, 862)	TP=117 (91, 140) FP=76 (34, 158) FN=83 (60, 109) TN=724 (642, 766)
30%-70% AMM, females	6	1029	186	32.8 (15.9, 55.8) †	89.8 (77.9, 95.7)	TP=16 (8, 28) FP=97 (41, 210) FN=34 (22, 42) TN=853 (740, 909)	TP=33 (16, 56) FP=92 (39, 199) FN=67 (44, 84) TN=808 (701, 861)	TP=66 (32, 112) FP=82 (34, 177) FN=134 (88, 168) TN=718 (623, 766)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies included in this analysis were Alam 2018, Aung 2023, Bancone 2018, Hamid 2018, Ley 2017, Wepelmann 2017. • Alam 2018 and Bancone 2018 was classified as high risk of bias due to convenience, non-random sampling. Alam 2018 was also classified as high risk of bias in flow and timing domain. • Aung 2023 and Bancone 2018 had high concerns of applicability as the test was not performed in the near – patient setting. 								
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor								
30% AMM	6	4613	204	89.1 (68.2, 96.9)	99.6 (99.2, 99.8)	TP=45 (34, 48) FP=4 (2, 8) FN=5 (2, 16) TN=946 (942, 948)	TP=89 (68, 97) FP=4 (2, 7) FN=11 (3, 32) TN=896 (893, 898)	TP=178 (136, 194) FP=3 (2, 6) FN=22 (6, 64) TN=797 (794, 798)
70% AMM	6	4613	428	86.7 (72.8, 94.0)	95.7 (92.7, 97.5)	TP=43 (36, 47) FP=41 (24, 69) FN=7 (3, 14) TN=909 (881, 926)	TP=87 (73, 94) FP=39 (23, 66) FN=13 (6, 27) TN=861 (834, 878)	TP=173 (146, 188) FP=34 (20, 58) FN=27 (12, 54) TN=766 (742, 780)
30%-70% AMM, females	6	2226	78	66.4 (50.4, 79.4) †	95.1 (92.2, 96.9)	TP=33 (25, 40) FP=47 (29, 74) FN=17 (10, 25) TN=903 (876, 921)	TP=66 (50, 79) FP=44 (28, 70) FN=34 (21, 50) TN=856 (830, 872)	TP=133 (101, 159) FP=39 (25, 62) FN=67 (41, 99) TN=761 (738, 775)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies included in this analysis were Adissu 2023 Ethiopia and India, Alam 2018, Pal 2021, Zobrist 2021 and Pal 2018. 								

- Where study arms were reported for both venous blood and capillary blood the arm with higher sample size was included as some patient samples were represented in both arms
- Alam 2018 and Pal 2018 was classified as high risk of bias due to convenience, non-random sampling. Alam 2018 was also classified as high risk of bias in flow and timing domain. Regarding applicability Pal 2021 contains a set of contrived specimens.
- Data relating to Adissu 2023 Ethiopia and India were not published as standalone papers. Therefore, risk of bias analysis and applicability assessment was performed based on manufacturer supplied study protocols.

TP=True Positive, FP= False Positive, FN=False negative, TN=True negative

† high variability in sensitivity between studies.

‡ pooled estimate not obtained due to small number of studies

Threshold	Studies	Participants	Cases	Pooled sensitivity % (95% CI)	Pooled specificity % (95% CI)	Numbers in a cohort of 1,000 patients tested (95% CI)		
						Prevalence of 5%	Prevalence of 10%	Prevalence of 20%
30% AMM	11	6507	399	47.6 (17.8, 79.2) †	99.4 (98.5, 99.8)	TP=24 (9, 40) FP=6 (2, 14) FN=26 (10, 41) TN=944 (936, 948)	TP=48 (18, 79) FP=5 (2, 14) FN=52 (21, 82) TN=895 (887, 898)	TP=95 (36, 158) FP=5 (2, 12) FN=105 (42, 164) TN=795 (788, 798)
70% AMM	11	6507	886	73.6 (58.1, 84.9)	93.6 (88.8, 96.5)	TP=37 (29, 42) FP=61 (33, 106) FN=13 (8, 21) TN=889 (844, 917)	TP=74 (58, 85) FP=58 (32, 101) FN=26 (15, 42) TN=842 (799, 869)	TP=147 (116, 170) FP=51 (28, 90) FN=53 (30, 84) TN=749 (710, 772)
30%-70% AMM, females	11	3185	238	45.5 (26.5, 65.9) †	92.8 (87.0, 96.1)	TP=23 (13, 33) FP=68 (37, 123) FN=27 (17, 37) TN=882 (826, 913)	TP=46 (27, 66) FP=65 (35, 117) FN=54 (34, 73) TN=835 (783, 865)	TP=91 (53, 132) FP=58 (31, 104) FN=109 (68, 147) TN=742 (696, 769)

This analysis was performed on data from **Alam 2018, Aung 2023, Bancone 2018, Hamid 2018, Ley 2017, Wepelmann 2017, Adissu 2023 Ethiopia and India, Pal 2021, Zobrist 2021 and Pal 2018**. Applicability and risk of bias concerns are summarised in table 8.

TP=True Positive, FP= False Positive, FN=False negative, TN=True negative

† high variability in sensitivity between studies.

Table 10. Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor – Manufacturer thresholds								
30% Manufacturer	6	4613	204	100.0 (98.2, 100.0) †	97.0 (96.5, 97.5)	TP=50 (49, 50) FP=29 (24, 33) FN=0 (0, 1) TN=922 (917, 926)	TP=100 (98, 100) FP=27 (23, 32) FN=0 (0, 2) TN=873 (869, 878)	TP=200 (196, 200) FP=24 (20, 28) FN=0 (0, 4) TN=776 (772, 780)
70% Manufacturer	6	4613	430	91.4 (75.5, 97.4)	93.7 (85.8, 97.4)	TP=46 (38, 49) FP=60 (25, 135) FN=4 (1, 12) TN=890 (815, 925)	TP=91 (76, 97) FP=57 (23, 128) FN=9 (3, 24) TN=843 (772, 877)	TP=183 (151, 195) FP=50 (21, 114) FN=17 (5, 49) TN=750 (686, 779)
30%-70% Manufacturer, females	6	2209	53	52.9 (28.9, 75.7)†	94.7 (86.3, 98.0)	TP=26 (14, 38) FP=50 (19, 130) FN=24 (12, 36) TN=900 (820, 931)	TP=53 (29, 76) FP=48 (18, 123) FN=47 (24, 71) TN=852 (777, 882)	TP=106 (58, 151) FP=42 (16, 110) FN=94 (49, 142) TN=758 (690, 784)
Notes – Studies included in this analysis were Adissu 2023 Ethiopia and India, Alam 2018, Pal 2021, Zobrist 2021 and Pal 2018 . Applicability and risk of bias concerns are summarised in table 8.								

Indirect analysis – Carestart G6PD Biosensor versus Standard G6PD Biosensor (AMM thresholds)

Note: Indirect analysis was not undertaken for 30% and 30-70% (F) due to high variability between studies.

Table 11. Indirect comparison between Carestart G6PD Biosensor and Standard G6PD Biosensor (AMM thresholds)		
Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value		Carestart G6PD Biosensor

Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value				70%
			Number of studies	6
		Number of studies	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases) Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	59.2 (42.0, 74.3) (268/510) 89.8 (82.1, 94.5) (1327/1492)
Standard G6PD Biosensor	70%	6	86.3 (75.4, 92.8) (365/428) 95.7 (92.2, 97.7) (3984/4185)	27.1 (8.3, 45.9), p=0.005 5.9 (-0.7, 12.4), p=0.079

Indirect analysis – Test brands 30%

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Standard G6PD by SD, AMM Biosensor (Quantitative)	Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
	Number of studies	Number of studies	6	15
		Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases) Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	88.6 (72.4, 95.9) (172/204) 99.7 (99.1, 99.9) (4392/4409)	94.7 (89.7, 97.3) (867/943) 96.3 (93.8, 97.9) (8228/8609)
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor AMM (Quantitative)	6	88.6 (72.4, 95.9) (172/204) 99.7 (99.1, 99.9) (4392/4409)	-	6.0 (-5.4, 17.5), p=0.302 3.4 (1.3, 5.4), p=0.001
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	9	98.5 (95.6, 99.5) (457/466) 95.5 (91.1, 97.8) (4385/4684)	9.9 (-1.2, 20.9), p=0.081 4.2 (1.1, 7.3), p=0.008	3.8 (-0.1, 7.7), p=0.054 0.9 (-2.8, 4.5), p=0.650

Indirect analysis – Test brands 70%

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Carestart G6PD Biosensor, AMM (Quantitative)	Standard G6PD by SD, AMM Biosensor (Quantitative)	Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
	Number of studies	Number of studies	6	6	5
		Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)	58.6 (40.6, 74.5) (268/510)	86.3 (74.7, 93.0) (365/428)	52.5 (33.7, 70.5) (280/518)
		Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	90.4 (82.3, 95.0) (1327/1492)	95.7 (91.8, 97.8) (3984/4185)	97.1 (94.0, 98.6) (2063/2135)
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor AMM (Quantitative)	6	86.3 (74.7, 93.0) (365/428) 95.7 (91.8, 97.8) (3984/4185)	-	-	33.8 (12.5, 55.0), P=0.002 1.4 (-2.1, 5.0), p=0.431
Carestart G6PD Biosensor, AMM (Quantitative)	6	58.6 (40.6, 74.5) (268/510) 90.4 (82.3, 95.0) (1327/1492)	-	27.7 (8.0, 47.4), p=0.006 5.3 (-1.4, 12.1), p=0.122	6.1 (-20.0, 32.2), p=0.648 6.7 (0.3, 13.2), p=0.041
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	5	77.8 (61.5, 88.5) (411/549) 95.4 (90.7, 97.8) (2125/2259)	19.3 (-3.0, 41.5), p=0.089 5.0 (-1.9, 11.9), p=0.157	8.4 (-7.8, 24.7), p=0.310 0.3 (-4.0, 4.7), p=0.887	25.4 (1.8, 49.0), p=0.035 1.7 (-2.2, 5.7), p=0.384

Indirect analysis – Test types

Note: Indirect analysis was not undertaken for 30% due to high variability between studies.

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value			Quantitative tests	
				30%	70%
		Number of studies	Number of studies	11	11
		Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)	47.6 (17.8, 79.2) † (188/399)	73.7 (95% CI: 57.0, 85.5) (589/886)	
		Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	98.1 (95% CI: 96.4, 99.0) (6060/6108)	93.6 (95% CI: 89.1, 96.3) (5258/5621)	
Qualitative tests	30%	19	94.9 (95% CI: 89.4, 97.6) (997/1103) 96.2 (95% CI: 93.5, 97.8)	-	

			(9811/10353)		
	70%	6	70.6 (95% CI: 46.9, 86.7) (442/683) 94.9 (95% CI: 89.6, 97.6) (2448/2615)	-	3.1 (-22.2, 28.4), p=0.810 1.3 (-3.7, 6.4), p=0.606

† high variability in sensitivity between studies.

Heterogeneity analysis

Supplementary table 1. Summary of the sources of heterogeneity across studies														
Test and threshold	Number of studies	Age, n(%)			Sex, n(%)			Geographical location, n(%)			Reference standard, n(%)		Blood type, n(%)	
		Adults	Children	Mixed	Female	Male	Mixed	Africa	Asia	Other	Adjusted male median	Median of male without G6PD	Capillary	Venous
Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)														
30%	15*	11 (73.3)	3 (13.3)	1 (6.7)	1 (6.7)	3 (13.3)	9 (60.0)	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	0 (0.0)	12 (80.0)	3 (20.0)	4 (23.5)	13 (76.5)
70%	5†	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (60.0)	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	5 (83.3)
BinaxNOW G6PD (Qualitative)														
30%	2	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	1 (50.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (50.0)	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)														
30%	9~	8 (88.9)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)	1 (11.1)	0 (0.0)	5 (55.6)	3 (33.3)	6 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	8 (88.9)	1 (11.1)	1 (10.0)	9 (90.0)
70%	5	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (40.0)	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)
WST8/1-methoxy PMS assay (Qualitative)														
30%	3	2 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)
70% (Espino 2016(a))	1	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)
Carestart G6PD Biosensor by AccessBio (Quantitative)														
30%, Original	6	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	5 (83.3)	1 (16.7)	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)
70%, Original	3	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (33.3)	1 (33.3)	2 (66.6)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)
AMM	6	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor (Quantitative)														
30%, Original	5†	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	2 (40.0)	5 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)
70%, Original	5†	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	2 (40.0)	5 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)
AMM, Manufacturer	6*	5 (83.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	3 (50.0)	2 (33.3)	1 (16.7)	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (45.5)	6 (54.5)

*Number of studies is 16 for sex covariate. Adu-Gyasi 2015 (a), (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the three studies is that (a) consists of 205 participants, (b) consists of 119 male participants and (c) consists of 86 female participants.

Number of studies is 17 for blood type covariate. Espino 2016 (b), (c) use the same participants, as do Bancone (a), (b). Difference between four studies is that Bancone 2015 (a) and Espino 2016 (c) uses capillary blood samples, and Bancone 2015(b) Espino 2016(b) uses venous blood samples.

† Number of studies is 6 for blood type covariate. Espino 2016 (b), (c) use the same participants. Difference between the two studies is that (b) uses venous blood samples and (c) uses capillary blood samples.

~ Number of studies is 10 for blood type covariate. Bancone (a), (b) use the same participants. Difference between two studies is that Bancone 2015 (a) uses capillary blood samples and Bancone 2015(b) uses venous blood samples.

+ Number of studies is 7 for blood type covariate. Pal 2021 (a), (b) use the same participants, as do Zobrist 2021 (a), (b). Difference between four studies is that Pal 2021 (b) and Zobrist 2021 (a) uses capillary blood samples, and Bancone 2015(a) Zobrist 2021 (b) uses venous blood samples.

Heterogeneity analysis – effect of blood type on Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor (manufacturer thresholds)

Note: Heterogeneity analysis was not undertaken for 30-70% (F) due to high variability between studies.

Threshold	Source of heterogeneity		Number of studies	Total number of patients	Number of cases	Summary sensitivity (95% CI)	Summary specificity (95% CI)
30%	Blood type	Capillary	5	4312	175	100.0 (98.2, 100.0)	97.5 (94.3, 99.0)
		Venous	6	4551	200	100.0 (97.9, 100.0)	97.5 (94.6, 98.9)
	Difference (95% CI), p-value					*	0.0 (-2.8, 2.8), p=0.998
70%	Blood type	Capillary	5	4312	331	90.1 (69.8, 97.3)	91.2 (85.3, 94.9)
		Venous	6	4551	421	91.6 (75.3, 97.5)	95.1 (91.8, 97.2)
	Difference (95% CI), p-value					1.5 (-14.1, 17.1), p=0.851	3.9 (-1.4, 9.3), p=0.150

*Heterogeneity analysis was not undertaken with 30% due to no variability between studies in the sensitivity.

Heterogeneity analysis – effect of blood type on Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor (AMM thresholds)

Note: Heterogeneity analysis was not undertaken for 30-70% (F) due to high variability between studies.

Threshold	Source of heterogeneity		Number of studies	Total number of patients	Number of cases	Summary sensitivity (95% CI)	Summary specificity (95% CI)
30%	Blood type	Capillary	5	4312	175	86.0 (69.3, 94.3)	99.7 (99.2, 99.9)
		Venous	6	4551	200	84.8 (69.0, 93.3)	99.7 (99.2, 99.8)
	Difference (95% CI), p-value					1.2 (-15.4, 17.9), p=0.886	0.0 (-0.4, 0.4), p=0.950
70%	Blood type	Capillary	5	4312	329	84.9 (65.9, 94.3)	95.8 (92.8, 97.6)

	Venous	6	4551	421	87.9 (72.8, 95.1)	96.6 (94.3, 98.0)
	Difference (95% CI), p-value				2.9 (-14.4, 20.2), p=0.740	0.8 (-2.1, 3.6), p=0.600

Sensitivity analyses

Where sufficient data was available, a sensitivity analysis was undertaken at each QUADAS-2 domain by excluding studies that yielded a high or an unclear risk of bias following the QUADAS assessment.

Indirect analysis – Test types

Could the selection of patients introduced bias?

				Quantitative tests
				70%
Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value	Specificity difference (95% CI), p-value	Number of studies	Number of studies	6
			Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	94.2 (95% CI: 89.0, 97.1) (4631/4927)
Qualitative studies	70%	4	71.5 (95% CI: 45.7, 88.2) (350/485)	4.9 (-22.8, 32.6), p=0.727
			94.3 (95% CI: 87.5, 97.5) (1878/2008)	0.1 (-5.9, 6.2), p=0.975

† high variability in sensitivity between studies.

SA not undertaken for remaining risk of bias questions due to limited number of studies having low risk of bias.

Indirect analysis – Test brands 30%

Could the selection of patients introduced bias?

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Standard G6PD by SD, AMM Biosensor (Quantitative)	Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
		Number of studies	4	11
	Number of studies	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases) Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	77.5 (58.1, 89.6) (117/149) 99.7 (99.2, 99.9) (4130/4146)	96.9 (93.9, 98.4) (697/723) 95.6 (92.7, 97.4) (6519/6830)
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor AMM (Quantitative)	4	77.5 (58.1, 89.6) (117/149) 99.7 (99.2, 99.9) (4130/4146)	-	19.4 (3.3, 35.4), p=0.018 4.1 (1.8, 6.4), p=0.001
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	6	98.4 (95.6, 99.4) (382/389) 93.5 (87.4, 96.8) (3756/4042)	20.9 (4.9, 36.9), p=0.010 6.2 (1.7, 10.7), p=0.007	1.5 (-1.1, 4.2), p=0.260 2.1 (-2.9, 7.1), p=0.409

Could the conduct or interpretation of the index test introduced bias?

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
		Number of studies	10
	Number of studies	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases) Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	96.1 (88.0, 98.8) (733/794) 97.0 (92.3, 98.8) (6343/6609)

G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	5	98.6 (96.7, 99.4) (354/359) 93.8 (86.5, 97.2) (3221/3462)	2.5 (-2.2, 7.2), p=0.298 3.2 (-2.5, 9.0), p=0.275
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Could the reference standard, its conduct or interpretation have introduced bias?

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
		Number of studies	9
	Number of studies	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)	96.9 (90.6, 99.0) (725/831)
		Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	96.8 (90.9, 98.9) (5693/5948)
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	4	99.0 (97.0, 99.7) (299/302) 93.3 (83.0, 97.6) (2684/2898)	2.1 (-1.6, 5.8), p=0.270 3.5 (-3.9, 10.9), p=0.353

Could the patient flow have introduced bias?

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
		Number of studies	10
	Number of studies	Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)	93.1 (83.1, 97.3) (634/753)
		Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	96.8 (92.1, 98.7) (6010/6286)
G6PD Qualitative FST	4	98.6 (95.6, 99.5) (204/207)	5.5 (-1.2, 12.2), p=0.107

(Qualitative)		97.3 (96.5, 97.9) (2039/2145)	0.6 (-2.5, 3.6), p=0.718
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Indirect analysis – Test brands 70%

Could the selection of patients introduced bias?

Sensitivity difference (95% CI), p-value			Standard G6PD by SD, AMM Biosensor (Quantitative)	Carestart G6PD (Qualitative)
	Number of studies	Number of studies	4	4
		Pooled sensitivity (95% CI) (true positives/ cases)	84.7 (69.6, 93.1) (286/338)	61.0 (40.0, 78.5) (249/384)
		Pooled specificity (95% CI) (true negatives/non-cases)	96.4 (93.2, 98.1) (3774/3957)	97.9 (95.7, 99.0) (1740/1779)
Standard G6PD by SD Biosensor AMM (Quantitative)	4	84.7 (69.6, 93.1) (286/338) 96.4 (93.2, 98.1) (3774/3957)	-	23.8 (0.5, 47.0), p=0.045 1.5 (-1.3, 4.3) p=0.285
G6PD Qualitative FST (Qualitative)	4	71.6 (51.9, 85.4) (350/485) 94.1 (89.2, 96.9) (1878/2008)	13.2 (-7.5, 33.8), p=0.213 2.2 (-2.1, 6.6), p=0.313	10.6 (-16.0, 37.2), p=0.434 3.7 (-0.2, 7.7), p=0.065

SA not undertaken for remaining risk of bias questions due to limited number of studies having low risk of bias.